

D3.3

Report on the dynamical downscaling of climate and atmospheric impacts final version

Project name

Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes

Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069941

Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01

Co-funded by
the European Union

Dissemination level	Public (PU) - fully open
Type of deliverable	R - Document, report
Work package	WP3 – Atmospheric Forcing Modelling, Weather Now/Fore-Casting and Data Processing
Deliverable number	D3.3 Report on the dynamical downscaling of climate and atmospheric impacts final version
Status - version, date	Final – V1.0, 21/2/2025
Deliverable leader	FMI
Contractual date of delivery	31/12/2024
Keywords	Atmospheric Stressor, Wind Hazard, Climate Data, Weather Data, Downscaling, Large-Eddy Simulation, Meso-Scale Modelling

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Peer review 1	Zoltán Kovács	MAV	20/12/2024
Peer review 2	Joris Hardy	ULIEGE	28/12/2024

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Summary of changes
0.1	15/10/2024	FMI	First draft of document structure
0.2	29/11/2024	FMI	Draft with all the FMI contributions ready for internal review
0.3	3/1/2025	FMI	Draft with all the FMI contributions revised based on the internal review
0.76	19/2/2025	FMI (+AUTH)	Contributions from AUTH included
1.0	21/02/2025	FMI	Final submitted version

Legal Disclaimer

The PLOTTO project is co-funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Innovation Actions under grant agreement No. 101069941. The views set out in this deliverable are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that it is fit for any specific purpose. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use made of the information contained herein. The PLOTTO project Consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law.

Copyright © PLOTTO Consortium, 2022.

Table of contents

Quality Control	2
Version History	2
Table of contents	4
List of figures	5
List of tables	7
List of abbreviations and acronyms	8
Executive Summary	10
1. Introduction	11
1.1 Project information	11
1.2 Purpose of the deliverable	11
1.3 Intended audience.....	12
1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables	12
2. Methodology	13
3. Modelling Methods and Procedures	14
3.1 Wind downscaling to local site scale using high-resolution LES	14
3.2 Downscaling of other meteorological parameters to local site scale using meso-scale modelling.....	21
3.3 Treatment of the catchment-area scale data	26
4. Use cases	27
4.1 Target sites and site-specific climatic stressors and data to be downscaled.....	27
5. Results	31
5.1 Use Case C	31
5.2 Use Case A	48
5.3 Use Case B	61
6. Conclusions	73
7. References	75

List of figures

Figure 1: The root and nested domains for the use case C (Wallonia). The colour indicates terrain height. The rectangles with the domain-ids like N02 show the horizontal locations of the nested child domains. N04 and N06 are the highest-resolution domains having 2 m grid spacings. The spots Hermalle and Herstal are the meteorological stations and the spot in N07 is the RCM referencing point. The horizontal size of the root domain is 16 384 m by 18 432 m. 16

Figure 2: Flowchart describing the downscaling procedure for short-term wind prediction. The method utilizes open-access ICON-EU NWP model outputs for wind data, which is also used to determine dominant wind direction and speed at surface level. This determines which wind sector LES data subset is chosen from the pre-computed LES data set and how it is rescaled to correspond with the NWP-forecasted conditions. 18

Figure 3: Locations of the three pilot domains on the European map. 24

Figure 4: Definition of mesoscale nested grid for the domain of Wallonia. 24

Figure 5: Definition of mesoscale nested grid for the domain of Budapest. 25

Figure 6: Definition of mesoscale grid for the domain of Romania. 25

Figure 7: Aerial view of the whole Danube delta area (Google Earth, Data SIO, NOAA, U.S. Navy, NGA, GEBCO, Image Landsat/Copernicus, Image ©2024 CNES/Airbus, Image ©2024 Maxar Technologies). 27

Figure 8: Aerial view of the Danube delta in Sulina area (Google Earth, Image ©2024 CNES/Airbus). 27

Figure 9: Left: aerial view of the port of Budapest (Google Earth, Image ©2024 Maxar Technologies). Right a view just off one of the pier sections showing an old warehouse (© Antti Hellsten) as an example of large buildings potentially influencing the local wind conditions. 28

Figure 10: Left: aerial view of the river Meuse area near Liege. Right: closer views of part of the study locations. (Google Earth, Image ©2024 Maxar Technologies) 30

Figure 11 : Stored rasters of LES-modelled one-hour averaged u-component 10 m over the local river surface: wind sector 255 deg (a) and wind sector 285 deg (b). The numerical values of u are arbitrary here because of the nominal mean wind speed set in LES. However, the values in different wind sectors are comparable with each other because the magnitude of the wind forcing in LES is the same for each sector. 35

Figure 12 : Daily maximum ten-minute averaged RCM wind rose for the scenario RCP4.5 (left) and Downscaled daily maximum one-hour averaged wind rose (right) based on the RACMO22E / EC-EARTH data. 38

Figure 13 : Time-split 99th percentiles for the scenario RCP4.5 (left) and RCP8.5 (right). The period number [1,5] is on the horizontal axis. Solid lines are non-downscaled RCM data and dashed are downscaled. Color-coding is as follows. Red: RACMO22E / HadGEM2-ES, blue: RACMO22E / EC-EARTH, cyan: RCA4 / HadGEM2-ES, black: RCA4 / EC-EARTH and orange: RCA4 / MPI-ESM-LR. 39

Figure 14 : Exceedance-frequency maps of gust-peak exceedances of 21 m/s between $0 < z < 10$ m downscaled from RACMO22E / HadGEM2-ES (left) and RACMO22E / EC-EARTH data (right). The climate scenario is RCP4.5. Although the highest values are larger than 800, the color scale is cut to 100 to better distinguish the gustier locations. In this case the frequencies are not scaled by the time-series length. There are a few gaps in the data due to computational reasons. 42

Figure 15 : Wind roses for the scenario RCP4.5 based on the RACMO22E / EC-EARTH daily maximum 10-min averaged data as such (left) and as downscaled daily maximum gust wind data (right). 43

Figure 16: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for temperature regarding the period under consideration. 45

Figure 17: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for humidity regarding the period under consideration. 46

Figure 18: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for precipitation regarding the period under consideration. 46

Figure 19 : The model domains with the terrain height shown by colours. The sea level (green) is about 6 m above the lowest terrain point. Town of Sulina and the port are within the nested domain N03. Note that the colour scale is modified such as to show the sea surface ($z = 6$ m) by grayish blue colour instead of green to easier distinguish sea surface from low-level terrain surface. 49

Figure 20: The nested model domains N04 and N05 covering part of the sea-entrance area. Also, the RCM-referencing point location is indicated. 50

Figure 21 : Wind roses for the scenario RCP4.5 based on the RACMO22E / EC-EARTH daily maximum 10-min averaged data as such (a) and as downscaled daily maximum gust wind data at the sea entrance (b) and at the town and port area (c). 54

Figure 22 : Statistical measures of the wind downscaled to the sea entrance (a, b) and to the town and port area (c, d) as functions of elevation: mean (blue), 95th percentile (red) and 99th percentile (magenta) of the daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed (a, c) and the daily maximum gust wind speed (b, d). Vertical profiles show the statistics evaluated on each z-level between $z = 7$ m and $z = 47$ m. The markers show single-point statistics downscaled to the meteo station. The RCM data is for the scenario RCP4.5 and it is modelled by RACMO22E / EC-EARTH. 55

Figure 23 : Yearly exceedance rates of 21 m/s of daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed (blue) and daily maximum gust wind speed (red) as functions of elevation for the sea-entrance area (a) and the port area (b). The markers show single-point statistics downscaled to the meteo station. 55

Figure 24: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for temperature regarding the period under consideration. 58

Figure 25: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for humidity regarding the period under consideration. 58

Figure 26: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for precipitation regarding the period under consideration. 59

Figure 27 : The root and nested domains for the Use Case B (Budapest). The colour indicates terrain height. The rectangles with the domain-ids like N02 show the horizontal locations of the nested child domains. The horizontal size of the root domain is 9216 m by 9216 m. 62

Figure 28 : Locations of the meteo stations on top of the building-topography map covering the whole nested domain N03: 1) riverbank, 2) east end of the central basin and 3) south side of the central basin. The black rectangle shows the output domain. Only the part right from the dashed vertical line is used to compute the statistical measures as functions of z. Note that trees are also classified as buildings in the underlying DSM. The colormap ranges from 0 m (blue) to 20 m (white). 63

Figure 29 : Wind roses for the scenario RCP4.5 based on the RACMO22E / EC-EARTH daily maximum 10-min averaged data as such (a) and as downscaled daily maximum gust wind data at the meteo station 1 (b), station 2 (c) and station 3 (d). 64

Figure 30 : Statistical measures as functions of elevation: mean (blue), 95th percentile (red) and 99th percentile (magenta) of the daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed (a) and the daily maximum gust wind speed (b). Vertical profiles show the statistics evaluated on each z-level between $z = 7$ m and $z = 71$ m and the black vertical line is the limiting value 14 m/s. The markers denote the values at the points of meteo stations: 1 riverbank (circles), 2 east end of the central basin (squares) and 3 south side of the central basin (diamonds). The RCM data is for the scenario RCP4.5 and it is modelled by RACMO22E / EC-EARTH. 65

Figure 31 : Yearly exceedance rates of 14 m/s (blue) and 21 m/s (red) as functions of elevation : daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed (a) and daily maximum gust wind speed (b). The markers denote the values at the points of meteo stations: 1 riverbank (circles), 2 east end of the central basin (squares) and 3 south side of the central basin (diamonds). 66

Figure 32 : Maps of yearly exceedance frequencies of 14 m/s (left) and 21 m/s (right) daily maximum gust wind speed. The lowermost panels just show the area layout to give a better spatial reference. The exceedance maps at $z = 11$ m, $z = 23$ m and $z = 35$ m are shown in ascending order. The heights are relative to the water surface. Note the different colour scales for 14 m/s and 21 m/s exceedance frequencies. 67

Figure 33: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for temperature regarding the period under consideration. 69

Figure 34: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for humidity regarding the period under consideration. 70

Figure 35: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for precipitation regarding the period under consideration. 70

List of tables

Table 1: RCM-GCM pairs of which results will be downscaled. 20

Table 2: Specification and dimensions of OMS domains. 23

Table 3: Specification of the output of mesoscale modelling approach. 26

Table 4: Structure of the nested domain system. 31

Table 5 : Validation results of the RACMO22E downscaling for the climate scenario RCP4.5. P95 and P99 stand for 95th and 99th percentiles and E10 for the number of exceedances of 10 m/s. The observation data is from the Herstal station. 34

Table 6: Statistical measures of daily maximum one-hour averaged wind speed 10 m over the river surface in the climate scenario RCP2.6 based on the five available RCM-GCM combinations. For each RCM-GCM combination, the RCM results are given first and the downscaled results on the following row labeled “Downscaled”. P95 and P99 stand for 95th and 99th percentiles and E14 and E18 stand for the number of exceedances of 14 m/s and 18 m/s scaled by the time-series length in years. 37

Table 7: The same statistical measures as in Table 6 but for the climate scenario RCP4.5. 37

Table 8: The same statistical measures as in Table 6 but for the climate scenario RCP8.5. 37

Table 9: The same statistical measures as in Table 6 but for the historical climate 1971 - 2005. 38

Table 10: Statistical measures of daily maximum gust wind speed occurring between the river surface and 10 m height over the river surface in the climate scenario RCP2.6 based on the RACMO22E data. P95 and P99 stand for 95th and 99th percentiles and E21 and E28 stand for the number of exceedances of 21 m/s and 28 m/s scaled by the time-series length in years. 40

Table 11: The same statistical measures as in Table 10 but for the scenario RCP4.5. 40

Table 12: The same statistical measures as in Table 10 but for the scenario RCP8.5. 40

Table 13: The same statistical measures as in Table 10 but for the historical climate 1971 - 2005. 41

Table 14: Spatial scale on which the output of the RCM is incorporated in the statistical evaluation of Use Case C. 44

Table 15: Downscaled temperature-related Indicators for the use case of Wallonia. 47

Table 16: Downscaled precipitation - related Indicators for the use case of Wallonia. 48

Table 17: Statistical measures of daily maximum gust wind speed over the sea-entrance area between 7 and 47 m above the water surface in the climate scenario RCP4.5 based on the five available RCM-GCM combinations. For each RCM-GCM combination, the RCM results are given first and the downscaled results on the following

row labeled “Downscaled”. P95 and P99 stand for 95th and 99th percentiles and E21 stands for the average number of yearly exceedances of 21 m/s. 51

Table 18: Statistical measures of daily maximum gust wind speed over the sea-entrance area between 7 and 47 m above the water surface in the climate scenarios RCP2.6, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5 and the historical data 1.1.1971 - 31.12.2005 based on the RCM-GCM combination RACMO22E / EC-EARTH. 52

Table 19: Statistical measures of daily maximum gust wind speed over the sea-entrance area and the port area between 7 and 47 m above the water surface in the climate scenario RCP4.5 based on the RCM-GCM combination RACMO22E / EC-EARTH. 52

Table 20: Spatial scale on which the output of the RCM is incorporated in the statistical evaluation of Use Case A. 56

Table 21: Downscaled temperature-related Indicators for the use case of Romania. 60

Table 22: Downscaled precipitation - related Indicators for the use case of Romania. 60

Table 23: Spatial scale on which the output of the RCM is incorporated in the statistical evaluation of Use Case B. 68

Table 24: Downscaled temperature-related Indicators for the use case of Romania. 71

Table 25: Downscaled precipitation - related Indicators for the use case of Romania. 72

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ABL	Atmospheric Boundary Layer
AFDJ	Galati Lower Danube River Administration
AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
BME	Faculty of Transportation Engineering and Vehicle Engineering
BSZL	Freeport of Budapest Logistics Ltd
CFL	Courant-Friedrichs-Levy criterion
COP	Common Operational Picture
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
EURO-CORDEX	The European branch of the international CORDEX
EZM	European Zooming Model system
FMI	Finnish Meteorological Institute
GCM	Global Climate Model
HadGEM2	Hadley Centre Global Environment Model version 2
HRAP	Holistic Risk Assessment Platform
ICHEC	Irish Center for High-End Computing
ICON	ICOsahedral Nonhydrostatic (the global NWP model of Deutcher Wetterdienst)
ICON-EU	Nested regional ICON model for Europe region
IWAT	IWW Assesment Tool
IWW	Inland Water-Way

Abbreviation	Meaning
IMS	Incident Management System
LAD	Leaf-Area Density
LES	Large-Eddy Simulation
LU	Land Use
MAV	Hungarian Railway Services
MOHC	Met Office Hadley Centre
MPI-M	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology
MPI-ESM-LR	Max Planck Institute Earth System Model Low Resolution
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NWP	Numerical Weather Prediction model
OMS	Operational Meso-scale modelling System
PDF	Probability Density Function
RACMO	Regional Atmospheric Climate MOdel
RCA4	Rosby Centre regional Atmospheric model version 4
RCM	Regional Climate Model
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
RORO	ROll in / ROll out
RSOE	National Association of Radio Distress-Signalling and Infocommunications
SPW MI	Service Public de Wallonie
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
TKE	Turbulent Kinetic Energy
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UDG	Danubius University of Galati
ULiege	Université de Liège
UM	University of Maribor
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report, titled “**D3.3 -- Report on the dynamical downscaling of climate and atmospheric impacts Final version**”, presents the downscaling approaches, methods and results developed and employed for large-scale climatological and meteorological data in the PLOTO project Task 3.3. The large-scale data originates from Regional Climate Model (RCM) predictions for the future climate scenarios and from Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) model data for short term forecasts. The selection of the climatological data from the EURO-CORDEX database has been reported in the deliverable report D3.1. The short-term data to be downscaled is obtained from the ICON-EU NWP system. Downscaling of the future climate projections addresses the STO 2 of PLOTO “Reliable quantification of climatic, hydrological and atmospheric stressors”, and the short-term downscaled forecasting addresses the STO 3 “Development of a forecasting module to provide high-resolution tailored weather and precipitation forecasts”. In addition, we describe the PLOTO use cases and their relevant weather vulnerabilities and hazards as a basis for selecting the data to be downscaled and designing the sets of resulting downscaled data.

As the resolutions of the RCM and NWP models are relatively low, they cannot capture any effects of local small-scale features of specific sites of interest like fine-grained terrain shape, buildings and trees. Therefore, the data must be downscaled to local scale and high resolution so that the effects of the local features are properly captured.

We apply two downscaling approaches. For wind data, we apply an approach based on precomputed very high resolution Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) data and data fusion. For other meteorological variables of interest: temperature, relative humidity, cloud cover and precipitation we apply high-resolution meso-scale modelling. We present the results of all the downscaling tasks for all three use cases, their specific features and the results.

The downscaled RCM data for future-climate scenarios will be used as input to Task 3.6 for the assessment of the site-specific climate risk parameters and stressor indicators. In WP4, downscaled climatic projections will be used for infrastructure resilience assessment. The short-term downscaled forecasting systems developed here will be used in Task 3.4 to obtain tailored forecasts for the use case sites for the needs of dynamical data assimilation in Task 3.5 and in WP6 to support IWAT, Decision support system and Enhanced Visualization Interface.

1. Introduction

1.1 Project information

The project entitled **“Deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes (PLOT0)”** aims at increasing the resilience of the IWW and the connected hinterland infrastructures, especially under adverse conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents, and other kinds of hazards. In doing this, downscaled climate change scenarios will be combined with simulation tools and actual data, to provide operators an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at strategic and operational levels.

PLOT0 project consists in the deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies, and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes. An integrated tool is set up to allow relevant authorities to improve the efficiency of their infrastructures management. This tool is a combination of downscaled climate change scenarios with simulation tools and actual data. Six complementary avenues will be considered to achieve this integrated tool that will support relevant authorities and their operators for more effective management:

- Measure and use high-resolution modelling data for the determination and assessment of the climatic risk of the selected transport infrastructures and associated expected damages.
- Use existing data from various sources with new types of sensor-generated data (computer vision) to feed the used simulator.
- Utilise tailored weather forecasts (combining seamlessly all available data sources) for specific hot spots, providing real-time early warnings with corresponding impact assessment.
- Develop improved multi-temporal, multi-sensor UAV- and satellite-based observations with robust spectral analysis, computer vision and machine learning-based assessment for diverse transport infrastructures.
- Design and implement an integrated resilience assessment platform environment as an innovative planning tool that will permit a quantitative resilience assessment through an end-to-end simulation environment, running “what-if” impact/risk/resilience assessment scenarios. The effects of adaptation measures can be investigated by changing the hazard, exposure, and vulnerability input parameters.
- Design and implement a Common Operational Picture (COP), including an enhanced visualisation interface and an Incident Management System (IMS).

The PLOT0 integrated platform and its tools will be validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania and Hungary.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

Downscaling of the future climate projections addresses the STO 2 of PLOT0 “Reliable quantification of climatic, hydrological and atmospheric stressors”, and the short-term downscaled forecasting addresses the STO 3 “Development of a forecasting module to provide high-resolution tailored weather and precipitation forecasts”. The purpose of this deliverable report D3.3 is to describe the downscaling approaches, methods, procedures and results. Wind data is downscaled based on high-

resolution Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) modelling and data fusion while other meteorological variables: temperature, relative humidity, cloud cover and precipitation are downscaled based on high-resolution meso-scale modelling. This report describes not only the methodology for downsampling the RCM-predicted future climate data, but also a methodology for producing short term (for instance 24-72 hours) downscaled forecasts to the target sites by automatically on-line downsampling predictions of Numerical Weather Prediction Model (NWP). The motivation for the downsampling is to bring in the local effects of local small-scale features, such as fine-grained terrain shape and even buildings and trees. Such effects can be important when assessing the risks and vulnerability of assets, functions and operations, and they are not at all captured by RCMs and NWPs. The predecessor of this report D3.2 already presented and explained the methodologies. This report D3.3 is the final version reporting the final outcomes of Task 3.3. for all use cases with the detailed downsampling tasks and results per use cases and a description of the specific features in the procedures.

1.3 Intended audience

The primary audience of this deliverable report consists of the PLOTO partners involved in the tasks exploiting the final downscaled data and results, see Sec. 1.4. The secondary audience is the whole PLOTO consortium. In addition, as the dissemination level of this report is “Public”, it is open to any interested audience.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

The Deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 1. Describes PLOTO’s aim, as well as this document’s purpose, intended audience and structure.
- Section 2. Describes the context and general methodology of this Deliverable.
- Section 3. Describes the modelling approaches and techniques for the downsampling.
- Section 4. Presents the target sites of each use case and the use-case specific relevant climatic stressors, which in turn determine the detailed specification of the data to be downscaled.
- Section 5. Presents the use-case specific downsampling details and the results and their analyses for each three use cases.
- Section 6. Concludes the Deliverable by summarising the main outcomes.

The outcomes of Task 3.3 will be used as input to Tasks 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, as well as WP4 and WP6, as described in Section 2.

2. Methodology

This deliverable report (D3.3) is the final part in the “trilogy” of D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3. D3.1 described the Regional Climate Model (RCM) predicted climate data to be downscaled to very high local resolution. D3.2 reported the first part of the Task 3.3 work, the downscaling methods and procedures while this report D3.3 reports the final outcomes of the tasks per use case and a description of those specific features in the procedures not yet included in D3.2. Temporally Task 3.3 spans from M10 up to M28.

The downscaled climate model data for future-climate scenarios will be used in WP4, downscaled climatic projections will be used for infrastructure resilience assessment. The short-term downscaled forecasting systems developed here will be used in WP6 to support IWAT, Decision support system and Enhanced Visualization Interface.

The methodology is based on Task 3.1 and 3.2, whereas the end user needs are defined in WP2. In Task 3.1, relevant RCM data for future climate scenarios were selected and extracted from the EURO-CORDEX database, while in Task 3.2 high-resolution land-use maps and surface parameters were produced. These data are needed as input data for the meso- and local scale modelling for the downscaling studies described in this report.

The main part of the work of Task 3.3 is carried out in close collaboration between AUTH and FMI involving also partners with strong use-case specific knowledge and expertise such as ULIEGE, SPW MI, RSOE, BME, MAV, BSZL, AFDJ, UDG and UM.

Downscaling of the future climate projections addresses the STO 2 of PLOTO “Reliable quantification of climatic, hydrological and atmospheric stressors”. The short-term downscaled forecasting addresses the STO 3 “Development of a forecasting module to provide high-resolution tailored weather and precipitation forecasts”.

3. Modelling Methods and Procedures

3.1 Wind downscaling to local site scale using high-resolution LES

This section presents the relevant theoretical and numerical developments required by the downscaling methodology for wind related risks and hazards. First, the essential elements of the PALM LES model are introduced followed by a description of the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) turbulence simulation procedures, which consider the effect of the site-specific orography and topography. Next, downscaling-specific practises to set up the computational model for a target site are discussed. Then, the downscaling procedure itself is described. Finally, the state information (data to be downscaled, e.g. RCM wind data for the future climate) employed for driving the downscaling procedure is presented.

3.1.1 PALM LES Model

The PALM LES model (Maronga et al., 2015; 2020) is a finite-difference flow solver for atmospheric and oceanic flows. The model can resolve the effects of complex terrain, buildings and vegetation on the flow. PALM is based on the non-hydrostatic, filtered, Navier-Stokes-equations in the Boussinesq-approximated or anelastic form and it is designed to run efficiently in supercomputing environments. The dynamic solver core of PALM time-integrates the prognostic equations for the conservation of momentum, mass, energy, and moisture on a staggered Cartesian Arakawa-C grid. The effect of subgrid-scale turbulence on the resolved flow field is parameterized using a 1.5-order closure after Deardorff (1980) with modifications according to Saiki et al. (2000). Discretization in time is achieved by using a 3rd-order Runge-Kutta scheme in accordance with Williamson (1980) and spatial discretization for the advection terms is implemented with 5th-order advection scheme after Wicker and Skamarock (2002). The horizontal grid spacing is always equidistant, whereas gradual stretching is permitted in the vertical direction. The vertical grid spacing is typically set equidistant within the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) and, to save computational time, the stretching is only applied above the ABL in the free atmosphere. The lateral domain boundaries of the computational model are by default cyclic, but advanced non-cyclic inflow and outflow boundary conditions are implemented as well. Recently, PALM has been equipped with a LES-LES self-nesting capability (Hellsten et al., 2021). This feature is essential in downscaling applications where the effect of large-scale atmospheric turbulence on local urban wind conditions must be included.

3.1.2 LES Modelling Approach

Wind downscaling usually requires LES data of very high spatial resolution, especially in urban and other built environments where the surface-layer wind flow is strongly influenced by the buildings, street canyons and other features of the built environment, which are typically of relatively small scale. For instance, resolving turbulent wind flow within a street canyon adequately requires a LES grid spacing from 1 to 2 m while in non-built environment with complicated terrain shape, about 5 m grid spacing is usually sufficient. On the other hand, the modelling domain must be larger than the large turbulent flow structures within the ABL. This usually means that the horizontal domain coverage must be from about hundred square kilometres up to several hundreds of square kilometres. It is impossible to entirely cover such surface areas with a very high-resolution grid having grid spacings of the order of one meter. Therefore, we concentrate the highest resolution into the areas of principal interest and

their vicinity and use coarser resolution elsewhere. As the PALM model has constant horizontal grid spacing within a domain, we use an LES-LES self-nesting approach implemented in PALM (Hellsten et al., 2021). In this method the model set up consists of several LES-domains nested in each other and coupled dynamically. A smaller child domain with higher resolution is nested within its larger, lower-resolution parent domain. Child domains can act as parents for yet smaller child domains forming a cascade of nested domains. Child domains and cascades of children can also be set up parallel to each other. As an example of a nested setup the Use Case C (Wallonia) setup is shown in Figure 1. The outermost and largest domain of lowest resolution is referred to as the root domain. For the root domain, boundary conditions are needed on all boundaries, but for the child domains, explicitly set boundary conditions are needed only on the bottom boundary, which follows the terrain and building surfaces. This is because the boundary conditions for the other boundaries are interpolated from the parent solution at each time step as part of the coupling procedure.

The bottom surfaces of the domains follow the terrain and building surfaces. This information is input in the PALM LES model in the form of 2-D raster arrays including the terrain and building height for each vertical column of LES-grid cells. The raster data is input in the NetCDF format. The grid cells under the solid surface, terrain or building, are eliminated out from the numerical solution procedure, i.e., inactivated. Boundary conditions are set on all interfaces between active and inactive grid cells. The boundary conditions on horizontal grid-cell faces are based on the Monin-Obukhov similarity theory. Under neutral stratification these boundary conditions reduce to the logarithmic law of the wall conditions that are also applied to vertical solid surfaces. The effect of sub-grid-scale roughness is taken into account by an estimated roughness length that is set proportional to the grid spacing such that with lower resolution a higher roughness length is set. A more detailed description of the solid-surface boundary conditions is found in Maronga et al. (2015).

The effect of vegetation can be modelled as a momentum sink term depending on flow velocity, prescribed canopy drag coefficient, and Leaf Area Density (LAD) distribution input as a three-dimensional array. A corresponding sink term is also added in the transport equation of the sub-grid scale turbulent kinetic energy. Details are found in Maronga et al. (2015). The vegetation data must be obtained for instance from a DSM or other inventory. As an example, in this work we model the trees as described above in the Use Case C, but not in Use Cases A and B, since we do not have separated or separable building- and trees data available. In those cases, the trees must be treated as solid objects.

The simulations are initialized by first running a precursor simulation for the root domain only for a sufficiently long time, typically several hours, to pass all initial transients and to achieve a statistically stationary flow state. The precursor run is initialized simply by specifying horizontally constant vertical profiles for the flow variables throughout the domain. The motivation to run precursor simulations without the nest domains is to save computing time and capacity. With the relatively low-resolution root domain only, the time steps can be set considerably larger, usually by one order of magnitude, following the Courant-Friedrichs-Levy (CFL) criterion, than with the full nested setup, and precursor simulation thus runs much faster. The actual LES run including all the nest domains is then started from the stored final time step solution of the precursor run. The actual run also needs a short adaptation time before the data sampling can be started because the nest domains require some time to adapt to their higher resolution from their local lower-resolution initial states set by interpolating from their parent solutions.

As the nesting method allows the use of large root domains, we take the advantage of employing cyclic boundary conditions at the side boundaries. This is more straightforward than using non-cyclic

inflow/outflow conditions combined with some method to generate artificial turbulent motion at the inflow boundary. Obviously, the cyclic conditions do not usually fully reflect the real situations, but this does not introduce any significant error to the solution around the area of interest as the cyclic boundaries are set sufficiently far away from it. Near the cyclic boundaries, terrain shape and possible buildings must be flattened out. Top boundary conditions are set in a simplified way by just setting a slip-wall condition at the top boundary. The slip-wall conditions for the velocity field mean that the vertical velocity component is set to zero and the vertical derivative of horizontal components are set to zero allowing horizontal flow (Neumann condition). Therefore, the ABL height in the simulations is dictated by the domain height. A more realistic way would be to specify the initial potential temperature profile such that the upper part of the domain features a temperature inversion layer, which forms a natural ceiling for the ABL. We have observed that the surface-layer results are not sensitive to the top boundary conditions and not even to the ABL height (Auvinen et al., 2020). The slip-wall method is computationally more affordable and avoids the solution of potential temperature in case of neutral stratification.

Unlike inflow condition, the cyclic boundary conditions do not drive the wind flow. Therefore, the wind flow must be forced in one way or another or else the wind flow would die out gradually. We apply a constant volume force in the upper part of the domain to maintain constant total momentum in the domain.

Figure 1: The root and nested domains for the use case C (Wallonia). The colour indicates terrain height. The rectangles with the domain-ids like N02 show the horizontal locations of the nested child domains. N04 and N06 are the highest-resolution domains having 2 m grid spacings. The spots Hermalle and Herstal are the meteorological stations and the spot in N07 is the RCM referencing point. The horizontal size of the root domain is 16 384 m by 18 432 m.

3.1.3 Wind downscaling procedure – general description

Our approach to downscale wind fields to local scale and very high resolution is based on fusing pre-computed high-resolution LES data and larger-scale information such as data from a Regional Climate Model (RCM) or a Numerical Weather Prediction model (NWP) or observations from a nearby meteorological station depending on the purpose of the downscaling. LES data provides high-resolution information and brings in the small-scale effects of terrain shape, buildings, and vegetation. The larger-scale information provides the temporal large-scale state of the wind direction and speed at some selected point in the downscaling domain, i.e. the referencing point. This large-scale information is hereafter referred to as state information.

Statistically stationary LES simulations must be carried out for a set of representative meteorological conditions. Typically, such a set includes twelve 30-degree wind sectors to cover all mean-wind directions. The LES simulations are run with a nominal wind speed recorded and time averaged during the LES run at the referencing point (or points) corresponding to the location(s) of the state information, a selected grid node of a climate model or an NWP model or location of a meteorological station. It is assumed that the LES wind fields can be rescaled to any prevailing wind speed specified by the state information. The scalability is strictly justified only for neutrally stratified ABL, but we assume that the errors introduced by the scaling under non-neutral conditions are reasonably small, especially in heavy-wind conditions, which are the most relevant situations when it comes to wind hazards. We have so far limited the precomputations to neutrally stratified cases only, but this is only in order to save computational cost and storage space. The downscaling approach itself is not limited to neutrally stratified conditions. During the LES runs, time and space dependent wind fields are output from each LES run for selected sub-domains, depending on the purpose of the downscaling, and stored to form a set of data units covering the representative meteorological conditions.

In the data-fusion phase the state information time series and the LES data are combined to obtain time series of three-dimensional wind fields having high-resolution in both space and time. The temporal resolution of the state information is typically much lower than that of the LES. For instance, wind observations are usually available as ten-minute averages, and archived RCM results may be available every six hours or even just once a day for example. The temporal resolution of the state information depends on its source, and possibly also on the purpose of the downscaling. Typically, the state information provides the wind direction and speed in only one point in space. For each state time interval, the best matching meteorological condition data unit is retrieved from the precomputed LES data set. This LES data is then rescaled using the ratio of the state wind speed of the current time interval and the nominal LES wind speed at the same spatial point, the referencing point. The LES referencing wind speed is time averaged over the same time interval as the state information referencing wind speed to ensure that they correspond to each other. Downscaled wind forecasts can be produced this way to given target sites, for example by employing wind data in a specified grid node of an RCM or an NWP model as the state information. Unlike the RCM data or NWP-based forecast, such downscaled forecast will include the various complicated effects from the local small-scale complexities of the terrain shape, built environment and vegetation depending on the level of detail of the LES simulations.

The fusion method involves the assumption of pseudo-stationarity because each LES data unit is a statistically stationary time-series of the particular meteorological condition it represents. Therefore, the final result is a time series made up by combining a number of stationary LES-data intervals of length equalling the state-information time interval. The changes from one interval to another are

discontinuous. This is not entirely realistic since naturally also the large-scale changes of the meteorological conditions driving the small-scale dynamics are dynamic. However, this simplification is unavoidable as long as the downscaling is based on precomputed LES. On the other hand, this is not a problem in wind hazard studies in which only high-wind conditions and their occurrence and frequency are of interest and the dynamic changes of the state are not of interest.

3.1.4 Downscaling of ICON-EU weather-prediction model short term predicted wind data – technical description

Automatized and operational short-term forecasting of downscaled wind can be used to support operational preparedness with potential application to the early-warning module of IWAT.

The Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) model ICON-EU (Zängl et al., 2015) is chosen as the on-line source of the larger-scale, but frequently updated, weather forecast to drive the operational downscaling system. This choice is made because ICON-EU is a state-of-the art NWP model which provides continuously updated meteorological data for the entire Europe. The online data repository and the open-access data sources offer the most suitable framework for the presented short-term wind forecast downscaling system. The flowchart shown in Figure 2 offers an operational layout for the operational downscaled wind prediction tool. A precursor for this system has originally been developed within the PANOPTIS-project (www.panoptis.eu) and adapted and further developed here for the needs of PLOTO.

Figure 2: Flowchart describing the downscaling procedure for short-term wind prediction. The method utilizes open-access ICON-EU NWP model outputs for wind data, which is also used to determine dominant wind direction and speed at surface level. This determines which wind sector LES data subset is chosen from the pre-computed LES data set and how it is rescaled to correspond with the NWP-forecasted conditions.

The ICON-EU data repository is seen on the top of the left branch in Figure 2. Every 24 hours the system monitors the ICON-EU data repository and looks for the next ICON-EU forecast data to be downscaled. When the data becomes available it calls the downscaling system `meteo_predict.py`. As a first step, the script invokes a module `icon_data.py` which automatically retrieves the new set of the most recent ICON-EU forecast data files which describe the meteorological state of Europe. The ICON-EU data files are subsequently decompressed and converted from grib2 to NetCDF-format.

As a next step, module `icon_wind.py` interprets the received forecast data, aims into the area of the chosen PLOTTO use case site and determines the representative surface wind condition predicted for the next 72-hour period (which is also the time period for the downscaled wind gust and meteorological state forecast). We use the ICON-EU wind data at 10 m level from terrain surface, because the next higher level at which wind data is freely available on-line is at 900 hPa pressure-level, corresponding to roughly 900 m height measured from the sea level depending on the ambient surface air pressure. This is too high for our present LES domains. Ideally, the reference wind would be right above the surface layer, say roughly at 200 m height, but as mentioned above, such data is not freely available from ICON-EU. The problem in using the surface wind at 10 m height is that while the LES model resolves terrain shape-, building- and vegetation effects on wind, the NWP model ICON-EU does not. Therefore, the LES-model 10 m wind may not correspond to the ICON-EU 10 m wind. In this case we avoid this problem by setting the wind referencing point of the LES model in the middle of a relatively large plain area. Moreover, we intentionally ignore modelling of buildings and trees around the referencing point to make it better correspond to the NWP model. Then the system goes on to produce a downscaled forecast. In this case, the obtained ICON-EU surface mean-wind vector is used by the module `localize_rescale.py` first for selecting the best corresponding 30-degree wind sector from the pre-computed LES result dataset stored in an operational server at FMI. Subsequently, the `les_rescale.py` module rescales the data by the ratio of the current ICON-EU wind speed and the nominal time averaged wind speed recorded in the referencing point in the LES pre-computations as described in Sec. 2.1.3. Finally, after completing the current 72-hour period forecast, the wind-prediction tool automatically sends the forecast to the PLOTTO system. The forecast may contain for example the following information for each monitoring site:

- Maximum gust speed (m/s);
- 99th percentile gust speed (m/s);
- Mean wind speed (m/s) and its direction;
- Standard deviation of wind speed (m/s).

3.1.5 Downscaling of RCM-predicted future climate wind data – technical description

The procedure to downscale the RCM wind data for the future climate projections is in principle similar to that of the ICON-EU NWP data. However, in terms of programming it is a simpler procedure because no on-line data fetching, and continuous automatic operation are needed. Instead, the wind data from more than one RCMs for the target site is downloaded from the EURO-CORDEX database beforehand. The downscaling is then performed off-line for the selected RCMs and RCP scenarios.

Again, 10 m level wind data is used because the next lowest available RCM data level, 850 hPa pressure level, is too high for our LES setups. The problem of using 10 m wind described in Sec. 2.1.4 also applies in this case and the approach to avoid the problem is the same. For the Use Case C, we use the nearest RACMO and RCA RCMs' grid point as the referencing point as shown in Figure 1 (middle of N07). This

point is surrounded by a fairly flat area, thus there are essentially no complex-terrain effects, and we also intentionally ignore modelling buildings and trees in the child domain N07 surrounding the referencing point to make the LES-predicted and averaged wind in this point better correspond to the RCM-predicted wind.

Relevant EURO-CORDEX RCM data (Kotlarski et al., 2014) has been selected for the present work by Lehtonen et al. (2023). This includes several wind variables somewhat depending on the RCM-GCM model combination. Out of the available wind variables, the most interesting and useful ones for the present work are the daily maximum 10 min averaged wind speed and daily maximum gust speed. Unfortunately, these wind speeds come without wind direction information. Therefore, we use instantaneous wind-velocity components given every six hours to estimate the wind direction of the daily maximum wind-speed events. However, not all RCM-GCM-model combinations provide such wind-component information. Therefore, we will only use those model data which include both the every-6-hour component data and the daily maximum 10 min averaged and gust wind speeds, see Table . This is because the wind direction information is crucially important for the downscaling. The unknown wind direction corresponding to the maximum gust speed is estimated by the direction of the maximum 6-hour instantaneous wind speed. Naturally, this is somewhat uncertain, but this is the best that can be done with the available data. It is important to understand that this is not a drawback of the wind-downscaling method, but a drawback of the EURO-CORDEX database.

The RCM data spans from the beginning of the year 2006 to the end of 2099 or 2100 depending on the individual model run, see Table 1. In addition, we have historical data from all the model combinations spanning from the beginning of 1971 to the end of 2005.

Table 1: RCM-GCM pairs of which results will be downscaled.

RCM	Horizontal resolution	Number of vertical levels	Driving GCM	Time-series end date
RACMO22E	0.11 deg	40	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	30.12.2099 and 30.11.2099 for RCP4.5
RACMO22E	0.11 deg	40	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	31.12.2100
RCA4	0.11 deg	40	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	30.12.2099 and 30.11.2099 for RCP4.5
RCA4	0.11 deg	40	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	31.12.2100
RCA4	0.11 deg	40	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	31.12.2100

To give an example of a detailed downscaling procedure, the algorithm employed for the use case C heavy-gust analysis reported within the Section 5.1.1 is described below. It is important to note that the details of the procedure depend largely on the application and the purpose of the downscaling. For instance, in this relatively simple example the focus is only on the daily gust wind-speed maximums found over the river surface, not in producing full 3-D time dependent downscaled fields although it is fully possible. However, such full 3-D time downscaling would take much more disk storage space. When full time dependent 3-D fields are analysed, it is best to analyse the fields day by day, if possible, instead of storing all the daily fields for example for 95 (or 94) years' time period. Saving all the downscaled data would typically require hundreds of terabytes of storage space.

- For each LES-computed wind sector WD data set:
 - find the highest 10 min time averaged referencing wind speed $V_{\max10rLES}$ from the LES time series at the referencing point using sliding-window averaging of the wind speed and the corresponding wind direction and record them;
 - find the local instantaneous maximum wind gust speed V_{\maxgRiverLES} over the river surface $0\text{ m} < z \leq 9\text{ m}$ and calculate the ratio $R_{gLES}(WD) = V_{\maxgRiverLES} / V_{\max10rLES}$;
 - record the local direction WD_{\maxgRiverLES} of the peak wind gust.
- Scan through the RCM time series:
 - for each day, estimate the wind direction $WD_{\max10RCM}$ corresponding to $V_{\max10RCM}$ by the day's highest-speed instantaneous wind vector output every 6 hours (because neither WD_{\maxgRCM} neither $WD_{\max10RCM}$ are available as explained above);
 - downscale $V_{\max10RCM}$ by multiplying it by $R_{gLES}(WD_{\max10RCM})$ to obtain V_{\maxgDS} as the result.
 - compute the required statistical measures of V_{\maxgDS} over the 95 (or 94) year period.

In this procedure, the downscaling is made for the RCM-predicted daily maximum 10 min averaged wind speed, not to the daily maximum gust speed. This is referenced to the maximum 10 min averaged LES-predicted wind speed at the referencing point (the selected nearby RCM grid node). The RCM-predicted daily maximum gust speed is a parameterized value which is not as straightforward to associate with the LES-predicted wind speed at the referencing point.

3.2 Downscaling of other meteorological parameters to local site scale using meso-scale modelling

This section covers the developments required by the downscaling methodology for other meteorological parameters to local site scale using meso-scale modelling.

3.2.1 MEMO mesoscale atmospheric model

The mesoscale meteorological model MEMO (Moussiopoulos et al., 2012), which constitutes a main part of the EZM (European Zooming Model) system (Moussiopoulos N., 1995), is used for producing grid meteorological model simulations. MEMO is a three-dimensional, non-hydrostatic, prognostic mesoscale model for the simulation of mesoscale air motion and inert pollutant dispersion at the local-to-regional scale, over complex terrain, allowing multiple nesting.

The MEMO model is capable of efficiently producing simulated datasets of hourly meteorological parameters, such as wind speed and direction, temperature, turbulent kinetic energy (TKE), incident solar radiation, cloud cover (diagnostically) and relative humidity, as well as turbulence parameters like surface roughness, Monin-Obukhov length and friction velocity for each grid point and at multiple heights above ground level in a 3-dimensional geographical grid, covering the target region. These high-resolution downscaled datasets offer flexibility in terms of data extraction. Another important feature of MEMO is that it is also capable of simulating local circulation systems, such as mountain-valley winds, sea/lake breezes, as well as the urban heat island. These mesoscale atmospheric processes also affect local-to-regional scale dispersion phenomena. Therefore, MEMO is considered as a suitable scientific tool to generate such comprehensive meteorological data for the needs of meteorological downscaling, as well as atmospheric pollutant dispersion.

3.2.2 Mesoscale modelling approach

For the initialisation of MEMO, a number of vertical profiles of the key meteorological variables originating from the ICON-EU (Zängl et al., 2015) operational numerical weather prediction model are used. Such profiles are assimilated into the model calculations on a 3-hour basis. The grid structure of ICON global model is based on an icosahedral (triangular) grid of the earth's sphere. The forecast data are also provided in standard packages on an icosahedral (triangular) grid. Regarding the ICON-EU calculations, there is a tightly coupled two-way interaction between the ICON-EU regional model and the global ICON.

The native model grid has a horizontal grid spacing of 6.5 km, the output grid a grid spacing of 0.0625° (~ 7 km). In the vertical direction, ICON-EU relies on 60 levels up to a height of 22.5 km. Besides, the ICON-EU forecasts are available up to 120 hours from the four model runs at 00, 06, 12 and 18 UTC and up to 30 hours from the model runs at 03, 09, 15 and 21 UTC. The time interval for the forecast period up to 78 hours is one hour, while the forecast periods between +81 and +120 hours are covered by a 3-hourly time interval.

More specifically, the downloader module of the automated module undertakes the transfer of the ICON-EU data, processes them (the ICON-EU data files are initially decompressed and, as a second step, converted from grib2 format into ASCII), and stores them in a dynamic data pool, also part of the OMS (Operational Meso-scale modelling System) infrastructure, which is kept updated at all times. The scheduler selects only the most recent dataset for input to the MEMO model. Each of these processes keeps a separate event log and diagnostic files accessible through the OMS repository.

The OMS has been configured for three pilot areas in Belgium (Wallonia), Hungary (Budapest) and Romania. The configuration of the MEMO grid for all areas is shown in Table , while Figures 3-6 depict the domain extents and the topography layer providing a high-resolution representation of the topography for the model domain for all under consideration.

Table 2: Specification and dimensions of OMS domains.

Wallonia				
Coarse Grid			Units	UTM zone
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	662274	5568490	m	31 U
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	120	120	Cells	
X,Y size of each cell	2000	2000	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	240000	240000	m	
Fine Grid				
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	685702	5616158	m	
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	120	120	Cells	
X,Y size of each cell	250	250	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	30000	30000	m	
Budapest				
Coarse Grid			Units	UTM zone
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	352109	5257038	m	34 T
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	72	72	cells	
X,Y size of each cell	2000	2000	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	144000	144000	m	
Fine Grid				
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	352109	5257038	m	
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	144	144	cells	
X,Y size of each cell	250	250	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	36000	36000	m	
Romania				
Coarse Grid			Units	UTM zone
UTM Coordinates (X,Y)	635546	5002753	m	35 T
Number of cells in X,Y-direction	240	240	cells	
X,Y size of each cell	1000	1000	m	
Grid total extent (X,Y)	240000	240000	m	
Fine Grid				

Regarding the required high resolution topographical input data, they were derived from the satellite elevation datasets of NASA’s Shuttle Radar Topography Mission – SRTM/90 m database (URL1). Besides, thematic layers of land use data were obtained from the Corine Land Cover 2006 (URL2) database, which includes 44 land use (LU) types, which were reclassified to the seven LU types used in MEMO applications, namely water, arid land, few vegetation, farmland, forests, suburban and urban.

Figure 3: Locations of the three pilot domains on the European map.

Figure 4: Definition of mesoscale nested grid for the domain of Wallonia.

Figure 5: Definition of mesoscale nested grid for the domain of Budapest.

Figure 6: Definition of mesoscale grid for the domain of Romania.

The meteorological mesoscale module, based on MEMO and ICON-EU models, provides functionality for downscaling several meteorological parameter fields which, amongst other, include temperature, humidity, incident solar radiation, relative humidity, precipitation, cloud cover and of course wind intensity and direction. More specifically, model results are provided at an hourly basis for the current hour, as well as for the next three (3) hours as short-term predictions. After the simulations process has been completed, model results are processed in an automated way and a range of maps are produced for a number of predefined variables with the aid of suitable post processing tools based on

the object-oriented scripting language Python. Table depicts the specification of the mesoscale modelling approach output.

Table 3: Specification of the output of mesoscale modelling approach.

Parameter (unit)	Time reference	Spatial Resolution	Vertical Reference
Temperature (°C)	1 h	250 m	2 m
Relative Humidity (%)			
Wind Speed (m/s)			
Wind direction (°)			
Precipitation (mm)			Surface
Cloud Cover (%)			-

For downscaling future climatic series of the above variables, a combination of sampled dynamical downscaling and statistical downscaling is used. The first part of this approach involves a selection of 100 monthly periods chosen within a period of 100 years covered by the EURO-CORDEX database and is performed separately for each of the three use case areas. The selection of the periods follows a climate classification scheme previously applied by Favre et al. (2014).

The statistical downscaling part of the approach involves a construction of synthetic PDFs of the main meteorological variables based on the mapping of the sample dataset of dynamical simulations, using appropriate weight factors. In any case, the construction of a complete downscaled series for the entire 100-year period is computationally infeasible and will not be undertaken in the frame of this task. What is targeted instead, is to obtain consistent PDFs of occurrence able to represent probabilities of events with extremely long recurrence intervals, which could nevertheless significantly contribute to the total hazard. It should be noted that to this end, extracting statistics from EURO-CORDEX series alone will not suffice since the recurrence intervals could well exceed by a large margin the total length of the available series.

3.3 Treatment of the catchment-area scale data

The RCM-predicted catchment-area scale precipitation data collected for hydrological analyses and shown in the report D3.1 (Lehtonen et al., 2023) needs no downscaling. Instead, it is used as such directly from EURO-CORDEX database. The catchment is a cumulative process feeding water into the river from the whole large catchment area. Thus, it depends on spatially and temporally integrated cumulative precipitation within the area. Downscaling would bring no added value in such data and would also be computationally too heavy a task.

4. Use cases

4.1 Target sites and site-specific climatic stressors and data to be downscaled

This section presents the target sites of each use case and the use-case specific relevant climatic stressors, which in turn determine the detailed specification of the data to be downscaled.

4.1.1 Use Case A: Danube delta

The delta of Danube in Romania is a large area (see Figure 7). Wind is downscaled only for the Sulina area (Figure 8). Sulina is the area which is the very mouth of the middle branch of the delta of Danube on the shore of Black Sea. There, ships enter and exit the narrow river, and the area is quite

Figure 7: Aerial view of the whole Danube delta area (Google Earth, Data SIO, NOAA, U.S. Navy, NGA, GEBCO, Image Landsat/Copernicus, Image ©2024 CNES/Airbus, Image ©2024 Maxar Technologies).

Figure 8: Aerial view of the Danube delta in Sulina area (Google Earth, Image ©2024 CNES/Airbus).

windy. Seaworthy vessels do navigate in this lowest part of Danube, and such ships have typically much larger face area than typical river ships thus being more vulnerable to heavy wind conditions. There is a small town of Sulina and a small port in the town.

Downscaled wind data will be used to estimate the high wind gusts to which ships are exposed while entering and exiting the river. Heavy gusts may pose a safety risk for the ships manoeuvring into the narrow river and out to the Black Sea. Principally, RCM-predicted future climate wind data for RCP-scenarios (primarily RCP4.5) will be downscaled for further risk and other analyses. Two separate target areas are studied: the port and town area seen on the left-hand side of Figure 8 and the sea-entrance area seen on the right-hand side of Figure 8. The downscaling procedure is similar to the example described in Section 3.1.5 except that full three-dimensional data is analysed day by day and statistical measures are computed also as functions of height. Additionally, a downscaled and automatized short-term forecasting system can be developed based on downscaling NWP data.

Precipitation is downscaled to a high-resolution grid over the lower catchment area covering the St. George, main and Sulina branches (Figure 7). This will serve to estimate level fluctuations and flush flood events that are associated with the risk of overflows or low levels. Temperature and cloud cover series estimated at the same a very high resolution will be used to assess icing probabilities on water surface as well as on port assets. The high-resolution terrain and land cover used will ensure that these effects can be reported on a near-per-asset base, taking into account radiative and latent heat fluxes.

4.1.2 Use Case B: Port of Budapest

Budapest Port or the Csepel Freeport is located behind the eastern bank of Danube a few kilometres downstream from the center of Budapest. It includes three basins and their pier sections as shown in Figure 9. There is also a small petroleum terminal on the south side, but it is only partially visible in Figure 9. It is the principal port of Hungary. It can handle dry cargo, containers, breakbulk, RORO,

Figure 9: Left: aerial view of the port of Budapest (Google Earth, Image ©2024 Maxar Technologies). Right a view just off one of the pier sections showing an old warehouse (© Antti Hellsten) as an example of large buildings potentially influencing the local wind conditions.

refined petroleum products and crude oil. More than 2000 ships carrying 1,200,332 tonnes of cargo visited the port in 2021 (<https://www.marineinsight.com/know-more/ports-in-hungary>).

Downscaled wind information is needed to identify the local exceedances of the wind-speed safety limit of the conventional ship loading and unloading operations in the Budapest port. Here, conventional means loading and unloading by cranes in contrast to roll in / roll out (RORO) type operations. For this purpose, we will store the instantaneous LES-predicted wind-speed components with high 0.33 Hz frequency covering the central basin and its piers and the three Vaisala WXT 536 weather stations installed in the port area. The study focuses to the central basin, because there are no crane operations at the northern basin and at the petroleum terminal. The precomputed LES data will then be used for wind downscaling as described in Section 3.1.5 and in Section 5.2.1. This way we will obtain downscaled wind information about the exceedance frequency in future climate projections, and also downscaled information for near term forecasting. The downscaling is expected to bring in remarkable added value since the climate-model data and weather-prediction model data do not include any effects of local terrain shape, buildings and vegetation in the wind, especially the maximum gusts, and these missing effects are brought in from the precomputed LES data by means of the downscaling procedure.

Upstream measurements of water levels will be combined with precipitation estimates downscaled over the coarse area in order to identify exceedances of operational level limits in the day-to-day timescale, while precipitation downscaled over the fine domain will help identify flush flooding potential over local assets in smaller timescales, of the order of tens of minutes. Icing potential that could affect crane and RORO operations will be estimated on the basis of downscaled moving-average series of temperature and cloud cover in the high-resolution domain.

4.1.3 Use Case C: River Meuse near Liege

The area of interest in the Use Case C is a section of the river Meuse (Maas) passing the city of Liege in Wallonia, Belgium and reaching downstream towards north up to the border between Belgium and the Netherlands (Figure 10). In this area the river consists of two branches near each other. The eastern branch is the natural river which is not navigable, and the western branch is a man-made channel (Albert canal) for ships to navigate. This branch flows partially above the surrounding terrain between dikes. Both branches have several ship locks in this area and there are several ports and smaller ship-loading piers in the area.

Figure 10: Left: aerial view of the river Meuse area near Liege. Right: closer views of part of the study locations. (Google Earth, Image ©2024 Maxar Technologies)

Downscaled wind information is needed for two specific purposes in this use case.

One purpose is to estimate the wave formation on the river surface in order to estimate the risk of overtopping past the riverbanks. The wave formation is mainly dependent on the time-averaged surface wind speed and the fetch length, which in turn depends on the wind direction relative to the river-bed direction. The wave formation itself will be separately modelled by ULiege using the downscaled average 10 m wind-speed and direction information over the whole modelled section of the riverbed, see Figure 1.

The second purpose is to estimate the high wind gusts to which ships are exposed to while manoeuvring on the river. The most critical manoeuvre is U-turn and the most critical vessel type is the container ship as their face area is typically quite large. The bulk vessels typically operated on rivers have only small wind-exposed face area and they are thus less sensitive to gusts. The tallest container ships operated on Meuse reach up to about 9 m above the water line. Therefore, we store instantaneous LES-predicted wind-speed components with high frequency of 0.33 Hz above the river surface up to at least 11 m height covering whole modelled section of the riverbed, see Figure 1. This precomputed LES data will then be used for downscaling as explained in Sec. 3.1.5 and Sec. 5.1.1.

Probability of exceedance of operational level limits and probability of overflow/breach events will be estimated on the basis of downscaled precipitation over the coarse domain. Such exceedances can directly affect traffic and manoeuvring operations due to overheight and draft limitations. The temporal resolution of this parameter is one hour, allowing the hydrological models to adequately resolve the propagation of flood fronts throughout the region. Icing potential will be calculated for river and terrestrial areas around Liege using the high-resolution domain. Such effects are expected to impact road traffic, river surface and near-shore assets.

5. Results

The presentation of results is started from the Use Case C since the validation of the downscaling methodology is carried out using the Use Case C. After the Use Case C, the results for Use Case A, and finally for Use Case B are presented and discussed.

5.1 Use Case C

5.1.1 Wind downscaling

Wind case studies for Use Case C

For the Use Case C, wind downscaling studies are carried out for two purposes. One case study is for predicting the wave heights during high-wind episodes in the future-climate scenarios predicted by the RCMs. For this purpose, time averaged wind speed and direction 10 m over the river surface are needed. Here the motivation is the risk of dyke overtopping hazard. The second case study focuses on heavy-gust episodes over the river surface based on the downscaled RCM-predicted future climate scenarios. The motivation here is the ship-manoeuving safety. Both cases are studied by using data from the same set of LES runs.

Description of the LES modelling

The horizontal extent of the whole LES domain, see Figure 1, is made relatively large to set its outer boundaries far away from the areas of interest. This approach facilitates the application of simple and easy-to-use cyclic boundary conditions can be applied on the outermost, i.e. the root domain. The root domain horizontal dimensions are 16 384 m and 18 432 m, and its height is 1024 m counted from the lowest terrain point within the root-domain. In fact, the domain should extend even further north since the river is of interest up to the border of the Netherlands, but we had to restrict the domain size as shown in Figure 1 because we had no land use data covering the Netherlands side. Grid spacing in the root domain is 16 m in all directions. This is too low resolution to resolve the local effects from e.g. buildings. Therefore, resolution is focused around the areas of interest using the LES-LES self-nesting capability of PALM (Hellsten et al., 2021). The nested domains are coupled using one-way coupling. The grid resolution is refined in three stages. The resolution is the same in all directions in all the domains. In addition to Figure 1, the structure of the nested domain system is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Structure of the nested domain system.

Domain id	Parent id	Grid spacing, m	Note
Root		16	The root domain
N02	Root	8	Intermediate domain
N03	N02	4	Intermediate domain also used to collect results
N04	N03	2	First principal domain for collecting results
N05	N02	4	Intermediate domain also used to collect results
N06	N05	2	Second principal domain for collecting results
N07	N02	4	Domain for collecting the referencing data

Figure 1 The finest resolution nested domains N04 and N06 cover most of the river sections of interest. However, some parts of the river are only covered by N03 and N05 having 4 m grid spacing and there are also small gaps between the output domains in N03 and N05. This is because small compromises had to be made in sizing the nested high-resolution domains. Otherwise, the model setup would have become computationally too heavy. There is also one more nested domain N07 having 4-m grid spacing within N02. This covers the RCM referencing point (Lon = 5.619494 deg, Lat = 50.701488 deg) for downscaling and for both RCMs: RACMO22E and RCA4. The surroundings of this point feature fairly flat terrain, thus the LES wind at $z = 10$ m height from the local terrain surface in this area should correspond well to the RCM-predicted 10 m wind. In reality, there are some buildings in this area, but we intentionally neglect them in the LES model in the domain N07 to make the LES and RCM predictions better correspond to each other around the referencing point. The referencing point is also shown in Figure 1. Buildings and trees are modelled only in the high-resolution nest domains N03, N04, N05 and N06. In the root and N02 the resolution is too low to include buildings and trees. There, their effects are modelled simply by means of increased roughness length z_0 in the surface boundary condition. In the root domain we set $z_0 = 0.3$ m and in N02 and N07 it is 0.1 m while N03 and N05 it is 0.07 m and 0.03 m in N04 and N06. Other computational details are described in Section 3.1.2.

Time and space dependent wind-velocity components are output at 0.33 Hz frequency over the river surface covering from bank to bank for the whole section of interest. The horizontal spacing of the output grid is 4 m also in the highest-resolution domains N04 and N06. Vertically the output levels relative to the local river surface are 1 m, 3 m, 5 m, 7 m, 9 m, 11 m within the domains N04 and N06. Over those river-surface areas covered only by N03 and N05, the vertical output levels are 2 m, 6 m, 10 m above the river surface. The output grids are defined as a large number of relatively small rectangular patches in the LES model. These patches always include also some airspace over dry land. For the sake of convenience all the output data is post processed into single structured rasters covering the whole river surface section excluding all gridpoints over land surface. Furthermore, the data is restricted from four dimensional (x,y,z,t) to two dimensional (x,y) . How this is made in detail depends on the case study and it will be explained below separately for the wave-height modelling case study and the gust-study case study. Note that this postprocessing differs slightly from the original plan described in the report D3.2 in order to avoid unnecessary storage of huge amounts data.

We carry out the LES runs for 12 30-degree wind sectors under neutral stratification and store all the above-described results for all the wind sectors in a data set for post processing and consequently for downscaling. Furthermore, we store the wind component data in the referencing point in N07 at $z=10$ m above the local terrain surface and in the two meteorological stations: Hermalle ($z = 9$ m, Lon = 5.690157 deg, Lat = 50.727968 deg) and Herstal ($z = 30$ m, Lon = 5.628044 deg, Lat = 50.658395 deg). The measurement-point heights are relative to the local terrain surface. The station data is used to validate the present downscaling methodology.

Validation

Operational wind observations, needed for validation, are available in the area of interest from the two above mentioned meteorological stations Herstal and Hermalle near the riverbank. It must be understood that with these data it is only possible to validate the whole modelling entity, not just the downscaling alone or the RCM data alone. This is because there is no meteorological station in the location of the EUROCORDEX RCM grid points in the area. The validity of the downscaling relies on the validity of the LES-modelling and on the assumption of scalability of the wind field discussed in

Section 3.1.3. The LES model PALM has been validated previously in several studies, e.g. by Letzel et al. (2008), Kanda et al. (2013), Hellsten et al. (2021) and Auvinen et al. (2022).

The wind observation data is obtained from Wallonair.be (2024) and it spans from January 1st 2020 to January 1st 2024. The data from Herstal is considered as the primary reference data since the measurement height at Herstal is higher (30 m) than in Hermalle (9 m), and especially since the Hermalle data has much more missing values (11 876 equalling to 247.4 days or 17% in total) than the Herstal data (469 i.e. 9.8 days or 0.7% in total). Such a large number of missing data points may cause some bias on the representation of diurnal and annual cycles. Indeed, the statistics of Hermalle data show much less windy conditions than those of Herstal as seen in Table 5. The principal reason for this is probably the low measurement height and trees taller than the mast surrounding the station nearby. Wind in these conditions is strongly affected by the trees and other details and very sensitive to the leaf-area density distribution and other details which are uncertain. For these reasons, the Hermalle wind-observation data is judged too uncertain and only the Herstal data is used for validation. The Herstal station is located in a built area, but the mast height 30 m is adequate relative to the heights of the surrounding low-rise buildings.

The data is half-hourly, and half-hour averaged. Daily maximum half-hour averages are extracted from the half-hourly data for comparison since the RCM data and its downscalings are daily maximums. There is a slight inconsistency here since the RCM data is daily maximum 10-minute averaged wind speed. However, this probably causes only a minor additional uncertainty. As mentioned in the previous subsection, the LES data is stored exactly at the wind measurement point thus the downscaled statistics are compared at exactly the correct spot. In addition to comparing the downscaled data with the observations, also the original RCM data at the referencing point (one EUROCORDEX grid point) is compared with the observed data. It must be remembered that the referencing point is located in a totally different environment (on an open plateau outside the river valley at higher elevation, see Figure 1), thus it should differ remarkably from the wind speed data measured in built environment in the river valley. It must be kept in mind that this is the main motivation of downscaling the RCM data.

Only the scenario RCP4.5 is discussed here, since the results for the validation points are very similar in the other two scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. Both available RCMs, RACMO22E and RCA4 are evaluated since their results differ considerably from each other. Only one driving GCM, namely ICHEC-EC-EARTH is chosen because the effect of the choice of the driving GCM is observed to be negligibly small. Four statistical measures characterizing the daily maximum 10 min averaged wind speeds for the four-year period data are computed and compared:

- averages,
- 95th percentiles,
- 99th percentiles,
- numbers of exceedances of 10 m/s.

The results are shown in Table 5. It is clear that RACMO22E predicts significantly higher wind speeds than observed. This is as expected and as it should be because the RACMO22E grid point is on an open plateau outside the river valley and also because the RCMs cannot take into account any effects from terrain shape in the local scale and from built environment or forest. The downscaling corrects the wind speed statistics to a good agreement with the observation statistics. In contrast to the RACMO22E-based results, RCA4 predicts remarkably lower wind speeds. It may seem that the original non-downscaled RCA4 results are in a good agreement with the observations and the downscaling

spoils the results rendering the wind speeds too low. But such a view is a misinterpretation for the above-described reasons. The wind speeds at the referencing point on an open plateau higher than the valley must be considerably higher than the wind speed measured in a built environment in the river valley bottom. Therefore, it is judged that the RACMO22E-result are more reliable than the RCA4-results at least in this case and the downscaled RACMO22E wind-speed statistics are sufficiently close to the observed statistics.

Table 5 : Validation results of the RACMO22E downscaling for the climate scenario RCP4.5. P95 and P99 stand for 95th and 99th percentiles and E10 for the number of exceedances of 10 m/s. The observation data is from the Herstal station.

RCM	Mean	P95	P99	E10
RACMO22E	7.3	12.0	13.9	220
RCA4	5.6	10.0	12.3	74
Observation	5.2	9.1	11.3	33
Downscaled from RACMO22E	5.5	9.6	11.0	55
Downscaled from RCA4	4.2	7.9	9.5	11

The wave-height case study

For this case the LES-predicted wind-velocity components u (velocity along the x-axis) and v (velocity along the y-axis) are horizontally restricted to over the water surfaces only, either selected (in N03 and N05) or interpolated (in N04 and N06) to 10 m height over the local river surface, and time averaged over the whole one-hour sampling period. One-hour averaging was chosen instead of the usual 10-minute averaging, because the wave generation is a relatively slow process. These u - and v -rasters are then stored for all 12 wind sectors for the actual downscaling process which is explained in Section 3.1.3. As an example, two u -rasters are shown in Figure 11, one for the wind sector 255 deg and another for the sector 285 deg. In fact, there are a few relatively small gaps in the data due to computational reasons, but the gaps have been filled by interpolation in order to make the wave-height modelling easier.

Figure 11 : Stored rasters of LES-modelled one-hour averaged u -component 10 m over the local river surface: wind sector 255 deg (a) and wind sector 285 deg (b). The numerical values of u are arbitrary here because of the nominal mean wind speed set in LES. However, the values in different wind sectors are comparable with each other because the magnitude of the wind forcing in LES is the same for each sector.

The downscaling is made by a python script “downScaleWind2DMRiver.py” which inputs both the postprocessed LES data and the RCM wind data according to the user-specified RCM/GCM combination and climate scenario. The script produces the downscaled daily maximum one-hour averaged wind speed and direction day by day 10 m above the local river surface on a raster covering the rectangular area (738201.0 m, 649840.0 m, 743685.0 m, 661564.0 m) (lower left easting, northing, upper right easting, northing) in the coordinate system EPSG:3812 with false_easting = 649328.0 m and false_northing = 665262.0 m. Real numerical 10 m over the local river surface as seen also in Figure 11. This script and all the necessary input data has been delivered to ULiege on October 9th, 2024 for further work. ULiege further develops the script by implementing the wave-height modelling directly in it. The wave height modelling strategy is briefly described in PLOT0 deliverable report D4.2. The purpose of this choice of implementing the wave-height modelling directly into the wind downscaling script is to avoid storage and transfer of excessive amount of intermediate result data, i.e. the downscaled daily maximum wind fields for a 95-year period. Instead of storing and delivering all that intermediate data, we present here below some statistical measures of it for each climate scenario and based on different RCM-GCM pairs, see Table 1. The daily rasters are not saved or output by the script, instead the idea is that the daily wave-height estimation is made on the fly within the same day-loop as the wind downscaling. Then, any necessary wave-height statistics can be computed on the fly for each day and stored without storing all the wave-height fields for all days. The wave-height modelling and related river overtopping risk analyses are part of WP4.

First, the whole time series are considered and after that the time series are chopped into shorter sub-intervals to identify possible trends. The following statistical measures are presented to describe the downscaled temporal distribution of daily maximum one-hour averaged wind speed 10 m over the river surface: mean, 95th percentile, 99th percentile and number of exceedances of wind speeds 14 m/s and 18 m/s are given for the climate scenarios RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5 and the historical period spanning from the beginning of 1971 to the end of 2005 based on all five RCM-GCM combinations listed in Table 1

Table 6. The numbers of exceedances are scaled by the length of the time series in years to make them comparable, thus the unit is 1/year. For comparison, the corresponding non-downscaled figures, i.e. the RCM predicted results in the referencing point, are given too. These results are given in

Table 6 to Table 9.

The first and the most salient observation from these statistical measures is the large and systematic difference between the RACMO22E- and RCA4-results. The RCA4-predicted wind speeds are substantially lower than those predicted by RACMO22E irrespective of the choice of the driving GCM. It is well known that climate-model statistical results, tend to vary from model to model and therefore it is useful to study results from an ensemble of models rather than from just one or two models. In this case, only these five RCM-GCM combinations can be used because none of the other model-combination results in the EUROCORDEX data set include sufficient wind data for the present analysis. It was assumed that five model combinations would already form a small ensemble, but as pointed out above, it turned out that the choice of GCM has no significant influence on this difference implying that in this respect we essentially only have two ensemble members instead of five, and two results hardly could be considered as an ensemble. However, our validation against the four-year observation time series from two stations, described in the previous subsection reveals that the RACMO22E-results appear more reliable than the RCA4-results in this case. In addition, as RACMO22E-results are representing the worst case, we end up with more conservative conclusions and are more on the “safe side” by prioritizing the RACMO22E-results. The effect of downscaling appears different than that in the validation exercise shown in Table 5. In the validation the effect was to make the wind speeds smaller, but here it usually slightly increases them. The reason is that in the validation, the downscaling was made only for two fixed spots in space while here the downscaled values are the daily maxima over the whole study area. There seemingly are locations where the effects from orography or buildings render even the averaged wind speed higher than elsewhere as seen in Figure 11.

To also study the effect of downscaling in the wind direction, wind roses for both non-downscaled RCM results for the scenario RCP4.5 based on RACMO22E / EC-EARTH are shown in Figure 12. It must be remembered that, unlike the RCM wind rose, the downscaled wind rose is not a usual fixed-point wind rose, because the daily maximum occurs in different locations depending on the wind direction. The effects of downscaling on the wind roses are relatively minor in this case, but for example four spokes out of sixteen disappear completely in the downscaling. This is probably since the terrain shape and the built environment strongly favour high wind speeds in some locations and in some wind

directions. It is also possible that the relatively wide wind sectors used here produce some bias to the wind directions. The effects of the sector width will be studied in the future work.

Table 6: Statistical measures of daily maximum one-hour averaged wind speed 10 m over the river surface in the climate scenario RCP2.6 based on the five available RCM-GCM combinations. For each RCM-GCM combination, the RCM results are given first and the downscaled results on the following row labeled “Downscaled”. P95 and P99 stand for 95th and 99th percentiles and E14 and E18 stand for the number of exceedances of 14 m/s and 18 m/s scaled by the time-series length in years.

RCM	Driving GCM	Mean	P95	P99	E14	E18
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	7.0	11.9	14.3	4.51	0.0971
Downscaled		7.1	12.2	14.9	6.34	0.399
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	7.1	11.7	13.9	3.29	0.105
Downscaled		7.2	11.9	14.5	4.91	0.231
RCA4	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	5.3	9.6	11.7	0.367	0
Downscaled		5.4	9.9	12.3	1.09	0.0108
RCA4	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	5.4	9.6	11.6	0.368	0.0105
Downscaled		5.5	10.0	12.4	1.13	0.0210
RCA4	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	5.5	9.6	11.6	0.463	0.0105
Downscaled		5.6	10.0	12.4	0.926	0.0421

Table 7: The same statistical measures as in

Table 6 but for the climate scenario RCP4.5.

RCM	Driving GCM	Mean	P95	P99	E14	E18
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	7.2	12.2	14.7	5.91	0.140
Downscaled		7.2	12.4	15.2	7.69	0.475
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	7.1	11.8	13.9	3.31	0.158
Downscaled		7.1	11.9	14.4	5.02	0.347
RCA4	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	5.4	9.8	11.9	0.453	0.0108
Downscaled		5.5	10.2	12.7	1.38	0.0432
RCA4	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	5.5	9.7	11.8	0.652	0.0210
Downscaled		5.5	10.0	12.5	1.22	0.0421
RCA4	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	5.5	9.6	11.6	0.421	0.0105
Downscaled		5.6	10.0	12.3	1.07	0.0105

Table 8: The same statistical measures as in

Table 6 but for the climate scenario RCP8.5.

RCM	Driving GCM	Mean	P95	P99	E14	E18
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	7.0	12.0	14.4	4.86	0.129
Downscaled		7.1	12.3	15.0	6.69	0.529
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	7.1	11.7	13.8	3.16	0.0736
Downscaled		7.1	11.9	14.2	4.34	0.168
RCA4	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	5.3	9.7	11.8	0.334	0.0108
Downscaled		5.4	10.0	12.6	1.37	0.0647
RCA4	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	5.4	9.6	11.6	0.410	0.0105
Downscaled		5.5	10.0	12.3	0.968	0.0316
RCA4	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	5.5	9.7	11.7	0.442	0
Downscaled		5.6	10.1	12.5	1.21	0.0316

Table 9: The same statistical measures as in Table 6 but for the historical climate 1971 - 2005.

RCM	Driving GCM	Mean	P95	P99	E14	E18
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	7.2	12.2	14.5	5.76	0.0869
Downscaled		7.3	12.5	15.0	7.44	0.608
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	7.2	11.9	14.2	4.14	0.114
Downscaled		7.3	12.1	14.7	5.68	0.200
RCA4	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	5.4	9.8	11.8	0.377	0.0
Downscaled		5.5	10.1	12.5	1.13	0.0290
RCA4	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	5.6	9.7	11.9	0.485	0.0
Downscaled		5.6	10.0	12.4	1.11	0.0286
RCA4	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	5.6	9.6	11.7	0.485	0.0
Downscaled		5.6	10.0	12.4	1.28	0.0286

Figure 12 : Daily maximum ten-minute averaged RCM wind rose for the scenario RCP4.5 (left) and Downscaled daily maximum one-hour averaged wind rose (right) based on the RACMO22E / EC-EARTH data.

To study if the RCM-predicted and downscaled data show any systematic trend during the century, each time series is split into five equal-length periods, and the statistical measures are computed separately for each period. The 99th percentiles are shown in Figure 13 for the scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. Neither the original RCM results nor the downscaled ones show any significant trend. The same is true also in cases of other statistical measures and in cases of the scenario RCP2.6 and the historical data.

Figure 13 : Time-split 99th percentiles for the scenario RCP45 (left) and RCP8.5 (right). The period number [1,5] is on the horizontal axis. Solid lines are non-downscaled RCM data and dashed are downscaled. Color-coding is as follows. Red: RACMO22E / HadGEM2-ES, blue: RACMO22E / EC-EARTH, cyan: RCA4 / HadGEM2-ES, black: RCA4 / EC-EARTH and orange: RCA4 / MPI-ESM-LR.

In summary, the following conclusions can be drawn from the results of this case study.

- Based on the validation RACMO22E-results are considered more reliable than the RCA4-results
- Downscaling systematically makes the high wind-speed tail of the wind-speed probability density distribution somewhat stronger compared with the non-downscaled RCM results as seen especially from the 99th percentiles and the scaled exceedance counts.
- The choice of the driving GCM has only a relatively weak impact on the statistics (mainly seen on the exceedance counts).
- Downscaling does not have significant impact on the mean of the daily maxima.
- The results for different RCP-scenarios and the historical period differ surprisingly little from each other.
- Downscaling changes the wind rose only relatively little, but it makes the rose more asymmetric with some spokes totally disappearing.
- Nor the RCM data neither the downscaled data show any significant trend in time.

The heavy-gust case study

For this case study, the LES data for each wind sector is post-processed such that the time dimension is reduced away by taking only the wind-velocity components corresponding to the maximum wind speed in the LES time series. The vertical dimension is reduced by the same way by only taking the maximum wind speed value from each column reaching up to 10 m above the local river surface. This way the four-dimensional data sets are reduced to two-dimensional. This is formally similar dimension reduction as was made in the previous case study but here the reduction is based on finding maximums while in the previous case study it was based on restriction to a single height of 10 m above the local river surface and on time averaging. Otherwise, the statistical analysis is quite similar to the previous case study. Time series is formed consisting of the daily maximum gust wind speed and its direction. Then, the same statistical measures as in the previous case are computed and tabulated here. In addition, exceedance frequency maps will be shown with the gust wind speed threshold of 21 m/s, and wind roses of non-downscaled RCM wind and downscaled gust wind will be presented and compared. In this case study only RACMO22E-results will be shown because according to the

validation, they appear more reliable than the RCA4-results. The RCM wind data used in the comparisons include parameterized gust approximations.

The statistical measures: mean, 95th percentile, 99th percentile, and average numbers of exceedances per year of 21 m/s and 28 m/s are shown in Table 10 to Table 13. Downscaling quite clearly increases the mean of daily maxima even though the effect of the river valley is to reduce wind speed in comparison to the RCM-referencing point. This is as expected, since the downscaled wind is now based on highly resolved LES turbulence which depends on the local terrain shape, buildings and trees while in the RCM wind data, turbulence is only a rough approximation ignoring the above-mentioned effects. Also, the percentiles increase remarkably, 99th percentile increasing more than 95th. The exceedance rates of 21 m/s increase by a factor of about three while the 28 m/s exceedance rates increase by a factor of about 20 owing to the downscaling. Hence, the downscaling renders the high-wind-speed tail of the probability distribution heavier and longer.

Table 10: Statistical measures of daily maximum gust wind speed occurring between the river surface and 10 m height over the river surface in the climate scenario RCP2.6 based on the RACMO22E data. P95 and P99 stand for 95th and 99th percentiles and E21 and E28 stand for the number of exceedances of 21 m/s and 28 m/s scaled by the time-series length in years.

RCM	Driving GCM	Mean	P95	P99	E21	E28
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	11.4	19.1	22.9	8.77	0.216
Downscaled		13.0	22.9	28.4	29.7	4.25
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	11.5	18.7	22.2	6.36	0.116
Downscaled		13.1	22.3	27.4	27.0	2.87

Table 11: The same statistical measures as in Table 10 but for the scenario RCP4.5.

RCM	Driving GCM	Mean	P95	P99	E21	E28
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	11.6	19.6	23.6	11.2	0.248
Downscaled		13.2	23.2	28.5	32.8	4.58
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	11.5	18.9	22.3	7.3	0.221
Downscaled		13.1	22.4	27.3	26.8	2.66

Table 12: The same statistical measures as in Table 10 but for the scenario RCP8.5.

RCM	Driving GCM	Mean	P95	P99	E21	E28
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	11.4	19.3	23.1	9.51	0.259
Downscaled		13.0	23.0	28.3	29.7	4.15
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	11.5	18.7	22.2	6.74	0.126
Downscaled		13.0	22.2	27.0	25.8	2.49

Table 13: The same statistical measures as in Table 10 but for the historical climate 1971 - 2005.

RCM	Driving GCM	Mean	P95	P99	E21	E28
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	11.6	19.4	23.1	9.36	0.145
Downscaled		13.3	23.3	28.5	32.1	4.23
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	11.6	19.1	22.6	8.17	0.114
Downscaled		13.3	22.5	27.8	29.0	3.34

The exceedance frequency maps based on downscaled RACMO22E / HadGEM2-ES and RACMO22E / EC-EARTH data and on the threshold of 21 m/s are shown in Figure 14. They show that the heavy gust occurrence is not evenly distributed over the study area. There are a few areas with clearly higher exceedance frequency than elsewhere. One of these gusty spots is right at the Triligiport and another one hits the port of Ile Monsin. Yet one spot is on Kanaal van Monsin and on its north side. Kanaal van Monsin has a ship lock connecting the Meuse and the Albert canal. This is a harmful state of affairs because ships need to manoeuvre especially precisely at the ports and locks. The exceedance frequencies are not scaled by the length of timeseries, so the values are for the whole duration of the RCM runs. The highest values are larger than 800, but the colour scale is cut to 0 – 100 to clearly distinguish the gusty areas. The maps are based on RACMO22E / HadGEM2-ES and RACMO22E / EC-EARTH data are very similar to each other with the HadGEM2-ES driven RACMO22E-based map showing somewhat higher level of exceedances. The spatial distribution is almost the same in both versions.

Figure 14 : Exceedance-frequency maps of gust-peak exceedances of 21 m/s between $0 < z < 10$ m downscaled from RACMO22E / HadGEM2-ES (left) and RACMO22E / EC-EARTH data (right). The climate scenario is RCP4.5. Although the highest values are larger than 800, the color scale is cut to 100 to better distinguish the gustier locations. In this case the frequencies are not scaled by the time-series length. There are a few gaps in the data due to computational reasons.

To study also the wind-direction information, wind roses based on non-downscaled and downscaled RACMO22E / EC-EARTH data are shown in Figure 15. Here the RCM wind data is not the parameterized gust wind as in Table 10 to Table 13. Instead, it is the daily maximum 10-min averaged wind similarly as in the previous case study. The reason for this is that the parameterized gust wind data does not involve any direction information. Again, like in the previous case study, one must remember that, unlike the RCM wind rose, the downscaled wind rose is not a usual fixed-point wind rose, because the daily maximum occurs in different locations depending on the wind direction. In this case the wind rose changes remarkably owing to the downscaling. This is mainly because the downscaled wind data is now turbulent gust data unlike in the previous case study and the turbulent motion is resolved down to a few meters scale, but the RCM represents 10-min averaged wind. The wind rose from the downscaled data is much more asymmetric and concentrated than the RCM-data based rose. Five spokes out of sixteen have totally disappeared and the high gust wind speeds ($V_g > 20$ m/s) are completely concentrated between the gust wind directions from about 170 deg. to 235 deg. Here, also the wind direction is the gust direction instead of time averaged wind direction.

Figure 15 : Wind roses for the scenario RCP4.5 based on the RACMO22E / EC-EARTH daily maximum 10-min averaged data as such (left) and as downscaled daily maximum gust wind data (right).

In summary, the following conclusions can be drawn from the results of this case study.

- Downscaling leads to stronger and more frequent turbulence (gustiness) than the parameterized RCM gust wind
- Downscaling quite clearly increases the mean of daily maxima even though the general effect of the river valley is to reduce wind speed in comparison to the RCM referencing point
- 95th and 99th percentiles and exceedance rates show that the downscaling renders the high-wind-speed tail of the probability distribution heavier and longer
- The occurrence of heavy gust-episodes spatially varies surprisingly much over the river surface according to the exceedance-frequency maps
- Heavy gust regions cover both ports in the study area
- Wind gust direction of the heaviest gusts is strongly concentrated to the sector between about 170 and 235 degrees

5.1.2 Other meteorological parameters

Dynamical downscaling of Temperature, Humidity and Precipitation for Use Case C

The dynamical downscaling of non-wind parameters is performed using the operational application of a high-resolution, nested meteorological model, as outlined in section 3.2. Results of the pilot period of application indicate that the mesoscale model results for temperature demonstrate fairly good agreement with measurements. Nevertheless, the model systematically underestimates relative humidity. Additionally, discrepancies between model results and observational data are observed for precipitation. This is expected due to the relatively low spatial resolution used in the model results, which limits its ability to capture microclimatic effects in areas with complex terrains, abrupt topographical changes, and varied land uses.

Validation of the mesoscale system was performed throughout the operational period by means of comparison to available meteorological measurements in the case study area. A complete analysis of

the model performance is provided in Section 4.2 of the PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, “Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site-Specific risk parameters and stressor indicators”.

Statistical downscaling of Temperature, Humidity and Precipitation for Use Case C

The statistical downscaling of non-wind data for the Wallonia Use Case was applied as a means to obtain scale-corrected statistics of the corresponding variables for longer periods, present and future, which are not covered by the operation of the OMS, based on input from RCM. The statistical approach follows the methodology outlined in section 3.2, essentially a two-step process of extracting a transfer function for each of the three variables and then applying it in the long-time series provided by the RCM output. For all three variables, a linear transfer function was used with mixed levels of residual error.

Extraction of the transfer functions

In order to obtain a valid transfer function for the downscaling of temperature and humidity, two different spatial scales need to be explicitly defined: the coarse scale, representing the spatial scale on which the output of the RCM is incorporated in the statistical evaluation, and the fine scale, which represents the choice of point-wise or area-averaged information calculated by the dynamical downscaling process, i.e. the output fields of the MEMO model.

For Use Case C, the coarse scale is defined as the cells of the ICON-EU NWP model ingested as boundary conditions in the MEMO model, with a spatial extent displayed in Table 14.

The fine scale is defined differently for the three non-wind variables, with this definition reflecting the different scales on which point-wise or area-averaged information is relevant for the three variables:

Table 14: Spatial scale on which the output of the RCM is incorporated in the statistical evaluation of Use Case C.

Variable	
Variable	Spatial Reference
Temperature	Domain centre (Ile Monsin)
Humidity	
Precipitation	Domain average (Meuse Catchment)

For the extraction of a valid transfer function, mesoscale model output of an operational period between 1/8/2023 and 20/12/2024 was used. The corresponding scatter plots for the three non-wind parameters are shown in figures 16-18.

Looking at the temperature scatter plot, an almost linear relation can be discerned with a high value of R-squared. Deviations from linearity are noted for the lower and below-zero temperatures, where the mesoscale correction becomes more positive. The slope of 0.85 indicates that the regional model tends to underestimate local temperatures.

Relative humidity has a much less defined behaviour, indicating an important contribution of local transfer effects which cannot be accommodated by a simple linear relation. On the other hand, the lack of a well-defined bias between the scales indicates that a similar trend could not be extracted from the RCM output over long-term periods, at least using a fitting test of a practical length.

Nevertheless, a nominal fit with a slope of 0.91 and an intercept of 43% can be used to provide a first-estimate correction of local effects, always keeping in mind that the transport term (representing, among others, moisture transfer from the river and adjacent valleys) can well dominate any cross-scale effect.

In the following sections we ignore the corrections on relative humidity, since the long-term trend and extreme analysis both in the literature and in terms of standardized indices does not include this variable.

The precipitation fit shows good linear fit for each of the typical precipitation cells as they traverse the modelling area. As expected, different linear trends appear depending on how far away from the domain centre each precipitation parcel travels regarding a typical synoptic pattern. Again, while it is not possible to use statistical downscaling to extract correction terms for individual precipitation events, a usable fit for long-time series can be extracted, where events on the extreme ends of corrections tend to average out. Since precipitation is an integrated quantity, it should be noted that the units of the slope and intercept depend on the relative extents of the RCM and mesoscale domains, respectively. An effort has been made to scale both the dependent and independent variables to units very close to the standard units of mm of precipitation height used for the long-term analysis.

Figure 16: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for temperature regarding the period under consideration.

Figure 17: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for humidity regarding the period under consideration.

Figure 18: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for precipitation regarding the period under consideration.

Application of the transfer functions

For the long-term trend analysis, we follow the approach used for PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, “Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site-Specific risk parameters and stressor indicators”, namely the assessment of climate extremes in terms of the ETCCDI (Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices) indices. These indices are designed to characterize various aspects of the extreme events, such as their frequency, intensity, and persistence (Klein Tank et al., 2009). Specifically, the core set includes 27 indices related to ambient temperature and precipitation, which are widely used to assess and monitor trends in climate extremes (Peterson and Manton, 2008; Alexander et al., 2006). As indicated in Section 5.1.1 of the present Report as well in the results sections of PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, calculations based on the RCP4.5 scenario represent a good average for future climate, in particular for precipitation, while temperature indicators also exhibit a predictable variability in relation to other scenarios. Therefore, in the following tables results for RCP4.5 are presented.

For the calculation of mesoscale corrections, the linear transfer function is applied to all indicators possessing the same dimensions as the fitted variable. Corrected values of non-linear indicators like FD and ID were re-calculated after correcting each individual daily value for the entire climatic timeseries.

Results for the corrected temperature indicators are shown in Table 15. Based on the sensitivity analysis presented in sections 3 and 5.1 of the present report, and following the practice introduced in PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, results are indicated for the ICHEC-EC-EARTH GCM as downscaled by the SMHI-RCA4 model. This combination of models has been selected as indicative of the common trends revealed by all model combinations for the selected temperature- and precipitation-related indicators, based on the sensitivity analysis presented both in PLOT0 D3.3 as well as in the literature (Kotlarski et al., 2015).

Table 15: *Downscaled temperature-related Indicators for the use case of Wallonia.*

Period	FD		ID		TN10p		TN90p		DTR (degrees)	
	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO
Historical	2727	3007	313	404	14.38		13.76		8.93	10.16
2006–2040	2455	2738	196	208	9.73		18.07		9.20	10.48
2041–2070	1856	2088	140	172	9.92		17.92		9.46	10.79
2071–2100	1566	1771	109	110	12.4		15.46		9.40	10.72

It is evident that the introduction of the mesoscale correction shifts all of the temperature-related contributions by approximately +1.5 degrees, while DTR remains unaffected since the same shift is applied to both extremes of the diurnal range. The number of frost and icing days shows also a notable uniform increase, since the slope of the linear transfer function is also shifting the nighttime minima into more negative values. A piecewise-fit transfer function could potentially improve the representation of the mesoscale correction near this range of temperatures.

Corrected values of the precipitation-related indices are shown in Table 16. Since all the related indices analysed here have dimensions of absolute precipitation, the mesoscale correction of the daily timeseries is causing an almost uniform scaling of the predicted extreme precipitation height by a

factor of about 2.6 over the reference area. It should be noted that this factor represents the correction induced into the low-accuracy regional average provided by the RCM and better represents the localised precipitation expected in areas near the centre of the mesoscale domain. It is also evident from the fit in Figure 18 that a large uncertainty is introduced in the mesoscale correction due to the multiple routes a precipitation cell can take while traversing the study domain. In any case, the linear fit represents a conservative average-trend indicator which might not be representative of the precipitation behaviour during extreme events, as they are captured in the long-term climatic timeseries. A potential area of improvement would be the introduction of multi-variate or stateful interpolators, instead of the average trend line fit, in order to better capture the dynamics of this series.

Table 16: *Downscaled precipitation - related Indicators for the use case of Wallonia.*

Period	RX5day (mm)		R95pTOT (mm)		R99pTOT (mm)	
	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO
Historical	7	17	361.6	953.3	145.4	382.4
2006–2040	4	9	347.3	915.6	111.6	293.1
2041–2070	8	20	413.5	1090.4	187.9	494.5
2071–2100	5	12	423.8	1117.6	177.1	466.0

5.2 Use Case A

5.2.1 Wind downscaling

For the Use Case A, wind conditions around the small town and port of Sulina and the shipway entrance area from Danube to Black Sea are studied. The motivation is ship-maneuvring safety in the narrow shipway on the river and between the breakwater banks at the sea-entrance area. The town and the port are located about 6-7 km inland from the sea-entrance area, see Figure 19, but the surrounding landscape is very flat and open and thus it is not expected to strongly decelerate wind speeds around the port. On the other hand, the built environment in the town is expected to have a roughness effect locally influencing the wind field and amplifying its turbulence. Moreover, not only the typical river vessels navigate in this area, but also seaworthy vessels, which have typically remarkably larger face area than the river ships and are thus more vulnerable to heavy wind conditions. Wind downscaling studies are carried out separately to both target areas: the port area and the sea-entrance area to study the occurrence of heavy wind events which may influence safe shipping and port operations.

Description of the LES modelling

The LES modelling domain in this case covers part of the delta area of the middle branch of the river Danube where it flows into the Black Sea, including the small town of Sulina and its port, presented in Figure 19. The two areas of interest are the Port of Sulina area and the sea-entrance area of the shipway between the port and the Black Sea. The horizontal size of the modelling domain is about 15.4 km from west to east, times 6.1 km from south to north. The height of the domain is about 1.2 km from the lowest point of the area, which is six meters lower than the sea level and located to the south of the town. The model grid resolution in this largest domain (root domain) is 12 m in all directions. Within the root domain, there are two intermediate nested domains with grid spacing of 4 m in all directions; these are the nest domains designated N02 and N04. Each of these intermediate nests surrounds its inner nest of the highest grid resolution of 2 m in all directions; these are the nests

designated N03 and N05. The nested domains are coupled using one-way coupling. The boundary conditions and surface description as well as other computational details are described in Section 3.1.2. Topography data for the root domain and all the nested domains was obtained from Copernicus DEM - Global and European Digital Elevation Model (COP-DEM) data archives (<https://doi.org/10.5270/ESA-c5d3d65>). Tree height data from the Copernicus High Resolution Layer Tree Cover Density archive (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-tree-cover-density>) was used for the nests N02 and N03 located over the Sulina town. Building height data was added on top of the topography data due to limitations of separate availability. The original horizontal data resolution was 10 m for all the data. The surface roughness lengths z_0 were set to 0.3 m in the root domain, 0.07 m in N02 and N04 and 0.03 m in N03 and N05.

Figure 19 : The model domains with the terrain height shown by colours. The sea level (green) is about 6 m above the lowest terrain point. Town of Sulina and the port are within the nested domain N03. Note that the colour scale is modified such as to show the sea surface ($z = 6$ m) by grayish blue colour instead of green to easier distinguish sea surface from low-level terrain surface.

The purpose of the intermediate nests N02 and N04 is to enable the modelling of the areas of interest in the nests N03 and N05 in much higher resolution than that of the root domain while avoiding too large a jump in resolution over nested boundaries which would deteriorate the accuracy of the nested-domain solution. Nest N04 also covers the referencing point chosen from the EUROCORDEX climate model data set used for the downscaling of wind climate-model wind data. The chosen referencing point is located on the sea to have its vicinity as flat as possible. This way, the climate-model data and the LES data better correspond to each other as the climate models cannot capture any local terrain-shape effects on wind. There is a meteorological observation station located on the bank about 3.5 km north from the referencing point.

Figure 20: The nested model domains N04 and N05 covering part of the sea-entrance area. Also, the RCM-referencing point location is indicated.

The areas of interest are modelled in higher resolution with the two 2 m resolution nest domains. Nest N03 covers the town and the port of Sulina and its vicinity on the Danube River, to provide information about the effects of buildings on the wind field on the river and within the port area. Nest N05 covers the part of the shipway from the Black Sea to the river (here called the sea-entrance area), flanked by banks acting as breakwaters, see Figure 20. This area of interest was chosen because it is considered as probably the windiest part of the shipway with tall seaworthy ships entering and exiting the river. Time and space dependent wind-velocity components are output at 0.33 Hz frequency from subsets of the grids from the nests N03 (town and port), N04 (climate model referencing point) and N05 (the shipway entry to the Black Sea, including also the location of the meteorological observation station in the middle of the nest). From N03 wind velocity components are output on a grid with 8 m horizontal intervals from an area of about 850 m × 100 m over the river Danube and the riverbank to the South and 8 m vertical intervals between $z = 7$ m and $z = 47$ m from the river surface (6 levels). N04 outputs from an area of 200 m × 200 m around the referencing point at 8 m horizontal intervals and in z from the height of 10 m. The referencing LES wind is spatially averaged over this 200 m × 200 m plane. For the nest N05 the output from points at 4 m horizontal intervals for an about 328 m wide area over the shipway, at height of 6 levels with 8 m stride between $z = 7$ m and 47 m from the water surface was stored. The output also covers the location of the meteorological observation station in the middle of the nest N05.

Results

First, the same scalar statistical measures as for the Use Case C are computed for the sea-entrance area and shown in Table 17 and Table 18 for all available RCM / GCM combinations and for all climate scenarios and the historical RCM data. These statistical measures indicate the same behaviour as in Use Case C reported in Section 5.1.1. Like in Use Case C, RCA4 predicts more than 30% lower daily maximum 10-min average wind speeds than RACMO22E. However, the diagnostic gust parameterization of RCA4 gives almost equally much higher gust contribution leading to roughly the same daily maximum gust wind speeds than RACMO22E as seen in Table 17. However, in the downscaling the referencing is based on the daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed at the referencing point. This means that downscaling of RCA4-data fails similarly as in Use Case C, in which

the validation discussed in Sec. 5.1.1 indicated RACMO22E to be more reliable than RCA4. Therefore, all the detailed results hereafter will be based only on the downscaled RACMO22E-data. Table 17 also shows again, as in Use Case C, that the statistics are not sensitive to the choice of the driving GCM. Therefore, only data from EC-EARTH driven RACMO22E will be used in what follows. Moreover, Table 18 shows that the statistics do not vary significantly with the chosen climate scenario or historical data. Therefore, only data for RCP4.5 will be used from this point on.

The scalar statistical measures: mean, 95th percentile and 99th percentile based on downscaled RACMO22E data are typically about 25% to 30% higher than the same measures describing non-downscaled RCM data. The average yearly exceedance counts based on downscaled data are more than five times higher than those based on the original RCM data. Generally, the gust wind speeds are high in this area. Table 19 shows comparison of these statistical measures computed for the sea-entrance area and the port area. There is only one RCM-row in the table since the same RCM grid node is used for both target areas. It is seen that the gust wind speeds are slightly higher over the town and port area than over the sea-entrance area. This is because of the roughness effect of the built environment. Even though this roughness effect locally decelerates the mean wind over the built area and somewhat downwind, it strongly enhances turbulence and thus produces higher peak gust speeds. Indeed, spatially and temporally averaged turbulent kinetic energy downscaled in the port area is 3.38 J/m³ while in the sea-entrance area with very little roughness it is only 2.24 J/m³. This is yet another example of phenomena which climate modelling cannot capture, but the LES-based downscaling can do so.

Table 17: Statistical measures of daily maximum gust wind speed over the sea-entrance area between 7 and 47 m above the water surface in the climate scenario RCP4.5 based on the five available RCM-GCM combinations. For each RCM-GCM combination, the RCM results are given first and the downscaled results on the following row labeled “Downscaled”. P95 and P99 stand for 95th and 99th percentiles and E21 stands for the average number of yearly exceedances of 21 m/s.

RCM	Driving GCM	Mean	P95	P99	E21
RACMO22E	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	12.4	19.8	24.0	11.9
Downscaled		16.0	25.5	30.9	58.7
RACMO22E	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	12.1	19.5	23.4	10.3
Downscaled		15.8	25.0	30.1	55.6
RCA4	MOHC- HadGEM2-ES	11.3	18.9	23.1	8.2
Downscaled		10.9	17.7	21.5	4.62
RCA4	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	11.4	18.8	23.1	8.23
Downscaled		10.9	17.7	21.5	4.62
RCA4	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	11.6	19.2	23.7	9.86
Downscaled		11.0	17.6	21.4	4.31

Table 18: Statistical measures of daily maximum gust wind speed over the sea-entrance area between 7 and 47 m above the water surface in the climate scenarios RCP2.6, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5 and the historical data 1.1.1971 - 31.12.2005 based on the RCM-GCM combination RACMO22E / EC-EARTH.

Scenario	Mean	P95	P99	E21
RCP2.6 RCM	12.2	19.6	23.5	10.7
RCP2.6 Downscaled	15.8	25.0	29.9	55.9
RCP4.5 RCM	12.1	19.5	23.4	10.3
RCP4.5 Downscaled	15.8	25.0	30.1	55.6
RCP8.5 RCM	12.1	19.4	23.6	10.1
RCP8.5 Downscaled	15.7	24.9	30.0	54.2
Historical RCM	12.2	19.5	23.7	10.5
Historical Downscaled	15.7	24.9	30.1	55.6

Table 19: Statistical measures of daily maximum gust wind speed over the sea-entrance area and the port area between 7 and 47 m above the water surface in the climate scenario RCP4.5 based on the RCM-GCM combination RACMO22E / EC-EARTH.

Target area	Mean	P95	P99	E21
RCM	12.1	19.5	23.4	10.3
Sea-entrance area Downscaled	15.8	25.0	30.1	55.6
Port area Downscaled	16.8	26.8	32.2	77.0

Wind roses for describing the RCM-predicted daily maximum 10-min averaged wind, daily maximum gust wind downscaled to the port area, and to the sea-entrance area are shown in Figure 21. According to the RCM data the dominant wind directions are north, northeast and south. Similar distribution is seen in the wind downscaled to the sea-entrance area although the north spoke is missing, but the 22.5 deg spoke is stronger than that of the RCM data. However, the overall shape of the rose is quite similar to that of the RCM rose. This is to be expected, because in the sea-entrance area there are almost no orographic features which would change the local wind directions much from the RCM-prediction. The main difference between these two roses is that the RCM rose is for the daily maximum 10-min wind and the downscaled one is for instantaneous maximum gust wind, which obviously causes differences in the wind roses. On the other hand, the wind rose for the town and port area looks quite different with southerly wind being dominant. The built environment changes the turbulent wind flow pattern which is reflected by the changed wind rose.

The same statistical measures as those given in Table 17 and Table 18 for the whole domains of interest are also computed as functions of z ($7 \text{ m} < z < 47 \text{ m}$ over the water surface). These statistics are also computed based on single-point downscaling to the meteo station in the sea-entrance area. These are shown in Figure 22. Profiles show that the height dependence of these statistical measures is weak. The single-point statistics for the meteo station are considerably lower than the z -profile values at the same height. This is not surprising, because it is much more likely to find higher maximums in the whole

three-dimensional domain of interest at any given time instant than just in one spot in space – a quite severe limitation of measurements. This is one example of how LES-based downscaling can help interpret single point measurements. Yearly exceedance rates of 21 m/s of daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed and daily maximum gust wind speed are shown in Figure 23 as functions of elevation for the sea-entrance area and the port area. The increased gustiness by the town roughness effect is clearly seen here. The exceedance rates are more height dependent than the mean and percentiles shown in Figure 22.

Exceedance frequency maps of 21 m/s (not shown) indicate fairly equal spatial distribution of exceedance frequencies over the areas of interest, which is as expected because the area has very little orographic variation.

Finally, it is checked if the wind data shows any future trends, but just like in Use Case C, no significant trend was found in any of the climate scenarios RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.

In summary, the following conclusions can be drawn from the results of this case study.

- The dominant wind directions in the Sulina area are north, northeast and south
- Wind observations may underestimate the gust wind speeds even at the elevation of the meteo station
- Daily maximum statistics do not vary much with the height ($7\text{ m} < z < 47\text{ m}$) in this case except the exceedance rates which clearly increase with the height
- Daily maximum gust wind speeds are slightly higher in the port area owing to the roughness effect of the town
- No future trend was found in any of the future climate scenarios

a)

b)

c)

Figure 21 : Wind roses for the scenario RCP4.5 based on the RACMO22E / EC-EARTH daily maximum 10-min averaged data as such (a) and as downscaled daily maximum gust wind data at the sea entrance (b) and at the town and port area (c).

Figure 22 : Statistical measures of the wind downscaled to the sea entrance (a, b) and to the town and port area (c, d) as functions of elevation: mean (blue), 95th percentile (red) and 99th percentile (magenta) of the daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed (a, c) and the daily maximum gust wind speed (b, d). Vertical profiles show the statistics evaluated on each z-level between $z = 7$ m and $z = 47$ m. The markers show single-point statistics downscaled to the meteo station. The RCM data is for the scenario RCP4.5 and it is modelled by RACMO22E / EC-EARTH.

Figure 23 : Yearly exceedance rates of 21 m/s of daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed (blue) and daily maximum gust wind speed (red) as functions of elevation for the sea-entrance area (a) and the port area (b). The markers show single-point statistics downscaled to the meteo station.

5.2.2 Other meteorological parameters

Dynamical downscaling of Temperature, Humidity and Precipitation for Use Case A

The dynamical downscaling of non-wind parameters is performed using the operational application of the OMS module, as outlined in sections 3.2 and 5.1.2. Results of the pilot period of application indicate that the mesoscale model results for temperature are in good agreement with measurements, with the exception of relative humidity where the model systematically underestimates observed values. Additionally, discrepancies between model results and observational data are observed for precipitation. In the particular Use Case, this is expected due to the relatively low spatial resolution used in the model results, which limits its ability to capture microclimatic effects in areas with complex coastal structure.

Validation of the mesoscale system was performed throughout the operational period by means of comparison to available meteorological measurements in the case study area. A complete analysis of the model performance is provided in Section 4.2 of the PLOTTO Deliverable D3.4, “Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site-Specific risk parameters and stressor indicators”.

Statistical downscaling of Temperature, Humidity and Precipitation for Use Case A

The statistical downscaling of non-wind data for the Romanian Use Case was applied as a means to obtain scale-corrected statistics of the corresponding variables for longer periods, present and future, which are not covered by the operation of the OMS, based on input from RCM. The statistical approach follows the methodology outlined in section 3.2 and applied in section 5.1.2, essentially a two-step process of extracting a transfer function for each of the three variables and then applying it in the long-time series provided by the RCM output. For all three variables, a linear transfer function was used with mixed levels of residual error.

Extraction of the transfer functions

In order to obtain a valid transfer function for the downscaling of temperature and humidity, two different spatial scales need to be explicitly defined: the coarse scale, representing the spatial scale on which the output of the RCM is incorporated in the statistical evaluation, and the fine scale, which represents the choice of point-wise or area-averaged information calculated by the dynamical downscaling process, i.e. the output fields of the MEMO model.

For Use Case A, the coarse scale is defined as the cells of the ICON-EU NWP model ingested as boundary conditions in the MEMO model, with a spatial extent displayed in Table 20.

The fine scale is defined differently for the three non-wind variables, with this definition reflecting the different scales on which point-wise or area-averaged information is relevant for the three variables:

Table 20: Spatial scale on which the output of the RCM is incorporated in the statistical evaluation of Use Case A.

Variable	
Variable	Spatial Reference
Temperature	Sulina port
Humidity	
Precipitation	Domain Average (Lower Danube)

For the extraction of a valid transfer function, mesoscale model output of an operational period between 1/8/2023 and 20/12/2024 was used. The corresponding scatter plots for the three non-wind parameters are shown in figures 24-26.

As observed in Use Case C, an almost linear relation can be obtained for temperature with a high value of R-squared. In contrast to the Wallonia case, slight deviations from linearity are slightly noticeable only for the lower temperatures. The slope of 0.92 indicates that the regional model tends to underestimate local temperatures.

Relative humidity has a much less defined behaviour, indicating an important contribution of local transfer effects which cannot be accommodated by a simple linear relation. The mesoscale model seems to underestimate observed humidity. On the other hand, the lack of a well-defined bias between the scales indicates that a similar trend could not be extracted from the RCM output over long-term periods, at least using a fitting test of a practical length. Nevertheless, a nominal fit with a slope of 0.84 and an intercept of 34% can be used to provide a first-estimate correction of local effects, always keeping in mind that the transport term (representing, among others, moisture transfer from the river and across the coast) can well dominate any cross-scale effect.

As in Use Case C, in the following sections we ignore the corrections on relative humidity, since the long-term trend and extreme analysis both in the literature and in terms of standardized indices does not include this variable.

The precipitation fit shows good linear fit for each of the typical precipitation cells as they traverse the modelling area. As expected, different linear trends (although with similar correction slope) appear depending on how far away from the domain centre each precipitation parcel travels regarding a typical synoptic pattern. Again, while it is not possible to use statistical downscaling to extract correction terms for individual precipitation events, a usable fit for long-time series can be extracted, where events on the extreme ends of corrections tend to average out. Since precipitation is an integrated quantity, it should be noted that the units of the slope and intercept depend on the relative extents of the RCM and mesoscale domains, respectively. An effort has been made to scale both the dependent and independent variables to units very close to the standard units of mm of precipitation height used for the long-term analysis.

Figure 24: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for temperature regarding the period under consideration.

Figure 25: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for humidity regarding the period under consideration.

Figure 26: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for precipitation regarding the period under consideration.

Application of the transfer functions

For the long-term trend analysis we follow the approach used for PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, “Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site-Specific risk parameters and stressor indicators”, namely the assessment of climate extremes in terms of the ETCCDI (Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices) indices. As indicated in Section 5.1.1 of the present Report as well in the results sections of PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, calculations based on the RCP4.5 scenario represent a good average for future climate, in particular for precipitation, while temperature indicators also exhibit a predictable variability in relation to other scenarios. Therefore, in the following tables results for RCP4.5 are presented.

For the calculation of mesoscale corrections, the linear transfer function is applied to all indicators possessing the same dimensions as the fitted variable. Corrected values of non-linear indicators like FD and ID were re-calculated after correcting each individual daily value for the entire climatic timeseries.

Results for the corrected temperature indicators are shown in Table 21. Based on the sensitivity analysis presented in sections 3 and 5.1 of the present report, and following the practice introduced in PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, results are indicated for the ICHEC-EC-EARTH GCM as downscaled by the SMHI-RCA4 model. This combination of models has been selected as indicative of the common trends revealed by all model combinations for the selected temperature- and precipitation-related indicators, based on the sensitivity analysis presented both in PLOT0 D3.3 as well as in the literature (Kotlarski et al., 2015).

Table 21: *Downscaled temperature-related Indicators for the use case of Romania.*

Period	FD		ID		TN10p		TN90p		DTR (degrees)	
	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO
Historical	3165	3258	794	825	11.70		17.65		9.50	10.16
2006–2040	2659	2736	425	447	11.76		19.56		9.28	9.92
2041–2070	2064	2137	232	254	13.29		16.27		9.37	10.02
2071–2100	1825	1902	196	203	12.38		12.95		9.42	10.08

It is evident that the introduction of the mesoscale correction shifts the temperature-related contributions by approximately +0.8 degrees, while DTR remains unaffected since the same shift is applied to both extremes of the diurnal range. The number of frost and icing days shows also a notable uniform increase, since the slope of the linear transfer function tends to shift the nighttime minima into more negative values. A piecewise-fit transfer function could potentially improve the representation of the mesoscale correction near this range of temperatures.

Corrected values of the precipitation-related indices are shown in Table 22. Since all the related indices analysed here have dimensions of absolute precipitation, the mesoscale correction of the daily timeseries is causing an almost uniform scaling of the predicted extreme precipitation height by a factor of about 1.9 over the reference area. It should be noted that this factor represents the correction induced into the low-accuracy regional average provided by the RCM and better represents the localised precipitation expected in areas near the centre of the mesoscale domain. Looking at the “best fit” in Figure 26 it is evident that a moderate level of uncertainty is introduced in the mesoscale correction due to the multiple routes a precipitation cell can take while traversing the study domain. In any case however, this uncertainty is smaller than in the Wallonia case and the linear fit represents a conservative average-trend indicator with less accuracy in assessing extreme events within the long-term climatic timeseries. A potential area of improvement would be the introduction of multi-variate or stateful interpolators, instead of the average trend line fit, in order to better capture the dynamics of this series.

Table 22: *Downscaled precipitation - related Indicators for the use case of Romania.*

Period	RX5day (mm)		R95pTOT (mm)		R99pTOT (mm)	
	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO
Historical	6	11	270.22	520	101.7	195
2006–2040	10	19	289.61	557	101.38	195
2041–2070	14	27	319.47	615	164.8	317
2071–2100	12	23	302.03	581	108.17	208

5.3 Use Case B

5.3.1 Wind downscaling

For the Use Case B, the port of Budapest, wind downscaling studies are carried out to study the occurrence of heavy wind events which influence safe operation of the port. The wind speed-limit for docking and for crane-operations is 50 km/h, i.e. 14 m/s. Both daily maximum gust wind speed and daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed are studied.

Description of the LES modelling

The LES modelling domain covers southern parts of the city so that the area of interest, the Budapest port, is in the middle of the domain, see Figure 27. The horizontal size of the root domain is 9216 m times 9216 m, and its height is about 924 m measured from the lowest terrain point in the domain. Grid spacings in the root domain in horizontal directions are 12 m. Also, the vertical dimension starts with 12 m grid spacing and above 408-meter height it is gradually stretched up to 18 meters to make the domain high enough. Within the root domain, we set two nested higher-resolution domains around the area of interest. The outer nest domain N02 has 4 m grid spacing in all directions and the inner nest domain N03 has the finest grid spacing of 2 m in all directions, see Figure 27. The nested domains are coupled using one-way coupling. The background coordinate system is EPSG:23700 with `false_easting = 650 000.0 m` and `false_northing = 200 000.0 m`.

The nest N03 covers the port and the three weather stations. The nest N02 covers, in addition to the port and weather stations, the referencing point used for connecting the LES results with the climate model data and the railway yard located near the port. The area surrounding the referencing point is very flat with mainly low vegetation such as bushes. Building and tree data were only used in nests N02 and N03. The tree data could not be separated from the building data, because there was no separated data available. The roughness length z_0 was set to 0.6 m in the root domain, 0.07 m in N02 and 0.03 m in N03. The boundary conditions and surface description as well as other computational details are described in Section 3.1.2.

Time and space dependent wind-velocity components are output at 0.33 Hz frequency. In N03, the output area covers the piers of the central basin of the port and the three weather stations around the basin. The crane operations, which are most wind vulnerable, take place at the central basin. The horizontal spacing of the output grid is 8 meters. Vertically, data is collected every 4 meters up to 71 m measured from the river-surface height. In N02, the output includes the referencing point, the railway yard and the three weather stations in the port although they are covered by the more accurate N03 output. The purpose of weather-station output in N02 is to enable possible grid-resolution assessment. The data for each weather station is collected from one grid column at every 4 meters height up to the height of 32 meters from the river-surface height. The data from the referencing point is collected from one grid column with 4-meter vertical intervals up to 384 meters although the referencing is made only at $z = 10$ m. This way, also the vertical wind profile can be studied at the referencing point. For the railway yard the horizontal output-grid spacing is 16 m and its vertical spacing is 4 m up to $z = 32$ m from the river-surface height.

Figure 27 : The root and nested domains for the Use Case B (Budapest). The colour indicates terrain height. The rectangles with the domain-ids like N02 show the horizontal locations of the nested child domains. The horizontal size of the root domain is 9216 m by 9216 m.

Results

There are three meteorological stations in Port of Budapest (Csepel Freeport) to monitor weather conditions including wind speed and direction. Certain port operations are suspended for safety reasons if wind speed is observed to be too high. Here, LES-downscaled RCM wind data is used to give a broader picture of the wind field in the port area. This way also the representativeness of the meteorological station observations can be assessed, and deeper understanding of the wind conditions in the port can be achieved. First, wind is downscaled at the spots of the meteorological stations shown in Figure 28. Then, it is downscaled for the whole N03-output domain which covers the whole central basin and its immediate surroundings. As wind speed in average varies quite much with elevation and since the crane operations may reach up to considerable heights, the statistics of the downscaled wind speed is presented as a function of z . Both daily maximum 10-min averaged, and daily maximum gust wind speeds are presented using similar statistical measures as for the Use Case C.

As seen in Figure 29, the dominant wind direction is northwest, and the dominance is strong, based on the RCM data. Winds downscaled to the meteorological stations, especially to the stations 2 and 3 show very direction-selective behaviour. This is because these stations are strongly affected by the nearby buildings and structures channeling the wind flow. The wind data downscaled to the meteorological stations in Figure 29 (b, d) are daily maximum gust wind while the RCM data is daily maximum 10-min averaged wind. The RCM data is for the scenario RCP4.5 and produced by RACMO22E driven by the EC-EARTH GCM. In this case only data from RACMO22E / EC-ICHEC is downscaled and studied because the

validation discussed in Sec. 5.1.1 indicated RACMO22E to be more reliable in this case than RCA4. It was also observed in Sec 5.1.1 that the choice of the driving GCM had only negligible effects on the statistics in Use Case C. In this case the effects are slightly larger but still small. In the following, only the results for RCP4.5 are shown and discussed because the statistics computed for RCP8.5 and RCP2.6 are practically the same as for RCP4.5.

From the three-dimensional downscaled data, the maximum 10-min averaged wind speed is determined as a kind of virtual measure for which the dimension of the data for a given z-level is first reduced to one (time only) by taking spatial maximums over the level for all time instants. Then sliding 10-min (200 time steps) averages are taken starting from each of the first 1000 time steps. There are 1200 time steps in the LES data in total, so that 1000 10-min averages can be computed. Then the maximum out of these 1000 averages is chosen. These are virtual or fictive measures in the sense that they cannot be measured in the real world, because spatially the maximum can bounce from one place to another within the z-level any time. The maximum gust wind speed over a z-level is found following the same idea but without any averaging. The horizontal extent of the z-levels is shown in Figure 28 which shows the whole horizontal size of the nested domain N03, the meteo stations and the output domain. The statistical measures as functions of z are not computed over the whole output domain but only over the area on the right side of the vertical dashed line. The reason for this is that on the left side of the dashed line the wind speeds are on average higher because of more open area over the river surface. Therefore, that left-side area is not properly representative of the port conditions where buildings influence the wind field much more. Including also the left side in the calculation would bias the statistics towards more frequent higher wind speeds. The statistics are computed from the daily maximum values over the whole 95-year (or 94 year) RCM time series.

Figure 28 : Locations of the meteo stations on top of the building-topography map covering the whole nested domain N03: 1) riverbank, 2) east end of the central basin and 3) south side of the central basin. The black rectangle shows the output domain. Only the part right from the dashed vertical line is used to compute the statistical measures as functions of z. Note that trees are also classified as buildings in the underlying DSM. The colormap ranges from 0 m (blue) to 20 m (white).

Figure 29 : Wind roses for the scenario RCP4.5 based on the RACMO22E / EC-EARTH daily maximum 10-min averaged data as such (a) and as downscaled daily maximum gust wind data at the meteo station 1 (b), station 2 (c) and station 3 (d).

Figure 30 shows the vertical profiles of mean, 95th percentile and 99th percentile of the daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed and daily maximum gust wind speed. It also shows the same measures for the locations of the meteo stations using markers. The statistics for the meteo stations are systematically lower than the profile-values at the same height. This is as expected since the profile points reflect the situation over the z-levels depicted in Figure 28 rather than just a single spot. Obviously, it is more likely to find higher maximum wind speed value from a larger area than from a single point at any given time instant. Moreover, the local winds at the meteo stations 2 and 3 are more influenced by the nearby buildings than the z-levels involving 6549 datapoints with different locations relative to the building pattern and terrain shape. Moreover, the measurement height of each station is only about 5 m above the local terrain surface, which may not necessarily be properly representative for the whole vertical height range within which for instance crane operations take place. Figure 30 shows the exceedance rates of 14 m/s and 21 m/s for both daily maximum 10-min averaged and gust wind speeds.

The mean, 95th and 99th percentiles of the 10-min averaged wind speeds downscaled to the meteorological station spots are all well below the limit of 14 m/s, but the 99th-percentile profile does exceed the limit already on the ground level, and also the 95th-percentile profile starting from about 15 m above the water surface. The exceedance rate of 14 m/s shown in Figure 31 (a) shows that the average yearly number of exceedances of 14 m/s varies between about 8 and 40 below the height of 30 m from the water surface but the exceedance rates based on the data downscaled to the meteorological stations show almost no exceedances. 10-min averaged wind speed exceeds 21 m/s only rarely and only at elevated heights. Obviously, the gust wind speeds are higher than 10-min averaged wind speeds. The height variation of the gust-wind speed statistics is slightly milder than those of the averaged wind speeds, at least above $z=10$ m. This is as expected, because especially the buildings produce more turbulence in the building canopy than above it leading to higher and more frequent peaks within the building canopy. According to the exceedance profiles the gust wind speeds exceed the limit of 14 m/s for 40-80 times a year in average below $z=30$ m and even more on upper elevations. Also, the data downscaled to the meteorological stations 1 and 2 show exceedances for 2-3% of the days. A few yearly exceedances of 21 m/s also occur according to the exceedance profile, but the wind speed downscaled to the meteorological stations show no exceedances of 21 m/s.

Figure 30 : Statistical measures as functions of elevation: mean (blue), 95th percentile (red) and 99th percentile (magenta) of the daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed (a) and the daily maximum gust wind speed (b). Vertical profiles show the statistics evaluated on each z -level between $z = 7$ m and $z = 71$ m and the black vertical line is the limiting value 14 m/s. The markers denote the values at the points of meteorological stations: 1 riverbank (circles), 2 east end of the central basin (squares) and 3 south side of the central basin (diamonds). The RCM data is for the scenario RCP4.5 and it is modelled by RACMO22E / EC-EARTH.

Figure 31 : Yearly exceedance rates of 14 m/s (blue) and 21 m/s (red) as functions of elevation : daily maximum 10-min averaged wind speed (a) and daily maximum gust wind speed (b). The markers denote the values at the points of meteo stations: 1 riverbank (circles), 2 east end of the central basin (squares) and 3 south side of the central basin (diamonds).

Exceedance frequency maps are employed to see how the gusts are distributed spatially over the study area. These are two dimensional horizontal maps for each z-level indicating the estimated average number of yearly exceedances of given gust-speed threshold. The same two threshold values as in Figure 31 are selected here, 14 m/s and 21 m/s. Only three z-layers: $z=11$ m, 23 m and 35 m are shown here in Figure 32, The exceedance-frequency distributions include quite a lot of noise, but they still provide a general view of the spatial distribution. Gusts exceeding 14 m/s are relatively evenly distributed except at $z = 11$ m, the exceedance frequencies are higher over the basin than over the piers as expected. Also, the west end, the mouth of the basin and the Ferroport site have somewhat less exceedances of 14 m/s than the rest of the area. Heavier gusts with wind speed exceeding 21 m/s indicate somewhat higher exceedance frequencies around the east end of the central basin than the western part. This is not owing to the dominant northwesterly winds which produce more heavy gusts on the west part of the basin rather than east. It is mostly contributed by southerly and northeasterly winds and to some extent also easterly and west-southwesterly winds. Wind shading and channeling by large buildings play an important role on the local wind fields and their turbulence characteristics with different mean-wind directions.

In summary, the following conclusions can be drawn from the results of this case study.

- Northwesterly winds strongly dominate on the area
- Wind observations may underestimate the wind speeds elsewhere in the port area even at the observation elevation
- The probability of high wind speeds increases with the elevation
- The observation points cannot perfectly represent the wind conditions everywhere in the port area
- The east end of the central basin shows higher probability of strong winds than the west part of the port area
- Wind shading and channeling by large buildings have significant effects on the local wind field and turbulence
- No future trend was found in any of the future climate scenarios

Figure 32 : Maps of yearly exceedance frequencies of 14 m/s (left) and 21 m/s (right) daily maximum gust wind speed. The lowermost panels just show the area layout to give a better spatial reference. The exceedance maps at $z = 11\text{ m}$, $z = 23\text{ m}$ and $z = 35\text{ m}$ are shown in ascending order. The heights are relative to the water surface. Note the different colour scales for 14 m/s and 21 m/s exceedance frequencies.

5.3.2 Other meteorological parameters

Dynamical downscaling of Temperature, Humidity and Precipitation for Use Case B

An in the previous sections presenting results for Use Cases C and A, the dynamical downscaling of non-wind parameters for the Romania case is performed using the high-resolution mesoscale model employed in the OMS module, as outlined in sections 3.2 and 5.1.2. Results of the pilot period of application indicate that the mesoscale model results for temperature demonstrate fairly good agreement with measurements with a lower accuracy for relative humidity. Additionally, discrepancies between model results and observational data are observed for precipitation, due to the limited ability both of the RCM and the OMS to capture microclimatic effects in areas with complex terrains, abrupt topographical changes, and varied land uses.

Validation of the mesoscale system was performed throughout the operational period by means of comparison to available meteorological measurements in the case study area. A complete analysis of the model performance is provided in Section 4.2 of the PLOTO Deliverable D3.4, “Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site-Specific risk parameters and stressor indicators”.

Statistical downscaling of Temperature, Humidity and Precipitation for Use Case B

The statistical downscaling of non-wind data for the Budapest Use Case was applied as a means to obtain scale-corrected statistics of the corresponding variables for longer periods, present and future, which are not covered by the operation of the OMS, based on input from RCM. The statistical approach follows the methodology outlined in sections 3.2 and 5.1.2, essentially a two-step process of extracting a transfer function for each of the three variables and then applying it in the long-time series provided by the RCM output. For all three variables, a linear transfer function was used with mixed levels of residual error.

Extraction of the transfer functions

In order to obtain a valid transfer function for the downscaling of temperature and humidity, two different spatial scales need to be explicitly defined: the coarse scale, representing the spatial scale on which the output of the RCM is incorporated in the statistical evaluation, and the fine scale, which represents the choice of point-wise or area-averaged information calculated by the dynamical downscaling process, i.e. the output fields of the MEMO model.

For Use Case B, the coarse scale is defined as the cells of the ICON-EU NWP model ingested as boundary conditions in the MEMO model, with a spatial extent displayed in Table 23. The fine scale is defined differently for the three non-wind variables, with this definition reflecting the different scales on which point-wise or area-averaged information is relevant for the three variables:

Table 23: Spatial scale on which the output of the RCM is incorporated in the statistical evaluation of Use Case B.

Variable	
Variable	Spatial Reference
Temperature	Domain centre (Csepel)
Humidity	
Precipitation	Domain average (Hungarian Danube basin)

For the extraction of a valid transfer function, mesoscale model output of an operational period between 1/8/2023 and 20/12/2024 was used. The corresponding scatter plots for the three non-wind parameters are shown in figures 33-35.

Looking at the temperature scatter plot, an almost linear relation can be discerned with a high value of R-squared and negligible deviations from linearity at the two ends of the range. The slope of 0.96 indicates that the regional model only slightly underestimates local temperatures.

As in the two previously examined Use Cases (Sections 5.1.2 & 5.2.2), relative humidity has a much less defined behaviour, indicating an important contribution of local transfer effects which cannot be accommodated by a simple linear relation. Nevertheless, a nominal fit with a slope of 0.89 and an intercept of 35% can be used to provide a first-estimate correction of local effects, always keeping in mind that the transport term (representing, among others, moisture transfer from the river and adjacent valleys) can well dominate any cross-scale effect.

In the following sections we ignore the corrections on relative humidity, since the long-term trend and extreme analysis both in the literature and in terms of standardized indices does not include this variable.

The precipitation fit shows an almost linear behaviour for each of the typical precipitation cells as they traverse the modelling area, with two linear patterns dominating the scatter plot. As expected, different linear trends appear depending on how far away from the domain centre each precipitation parcel travels regarding a typical synoptic pattern. As discussed for Use Case A, while it is not possible to use statistical downscaling to extract correction terms for individual precipitation events, a usable fit for long-time series can be extracted, where events on the two linear trends, visible in Figure 35, tend to average out.

Figure 33: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for temperature regarding the period under consideration.

Figure 34: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for humidity regarding the period under consideration.

Figure 35: Scatter plot of the mesoscale model outputs for precipitation regarding the period under consideration.

Application of the transfer functions

For the long-term trend analysis, we follow the approach used for PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, “Report on Dynamic Data Assimilation methodology and site-Specific risk parameters and stressor indicators”, namely the assessment of climate extremes in terms of the ETCCDI (Expert Team on Climate Change Detection and Indices) indices. As indicated in Sections 5.1.1, 5.1.2 and 5.2.2 of the present Report as well in the results sections of PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, calculations based on the RCP4.5 scenario represent a good average for future climate, in particular for precipitation, while temperature indicators also exhibit a predictable variability in relation to other scenarios. Therefore, in the following tables results for RCP4.5 are presented.

For the calculation of mesoscale corrections, the linear transfer function is applied to all indicators possessing the same dimensions as the fitted variable. Corrected values of non-linear indicators like FD and ID were re-calculated after correcting each individual daily value for the entire climatic timeseries.

Results for the corrected temperature indicators are shown in Table 24. Based on the sensitivity analysis presented in sections 3 and 5.1 of the present report, and following the practice introduced in PLOT0 Deliverable D3.4, results are indicated for the ICHEC-EC-EARTH GCM as downscaled by the SMHI-RCA4 model. This combination of models has been selected as indicative of the common trends revealed by all model combinations for the selected temperature- and precipitation-related indicators, based on the sensitivity analysis presented both in PLOT0 D3.3 as well as in the literature (Kotlarski et al., 2015).

Table 24: *Downscaled temperature-related Indicators for the use case of Romania.*

Period	FD		ID		TN10p		TN90p		DTR (degrees)	
	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO
Historical	2337	1914	687	513	12.04		15.25		8.07	9.27
2006–2040	1698	1144	341	188	10.48		16.50		8.03	9.23
2041–2070	1073	669	167	87	13.11		16.39		8.08	9.28
2071–2100	882	556	154	85	12.33		17.34		8.08	9.28

It is evident that the introduction of the mesoscale correction shifts all the temperature-related contributions by approximately +1.3 degrees, while DTR remains unaffected since the same shift is applied to both extremes of the diurnal range. The number of frost and icing days shows also a notable uniform increase, since the slope of the linear transfer function is also shifting the nighttime minima into more negative values. A piecewise-fit transfer function could potentially improve the representation of the mesoscale correction near this range of temperatures.

Corrected values of the precipitation-related indices are shown in Table 25. Since all the related indices analysed here have dimensions of absolute precipitation, the mesoscale correction of the daily timeseries is causing an almost uniform scaling of the predicted extreme precipitation height by a factor of about 2.4 over the reference area. It should be noted that this factor represents the correction induced into the low-accuracy regional average provided by the RCM and better represents the localised precipitation expected in areas near the centre of the mesoscale domain. It is also evident from the fit in Figure 35 that a degree of uncertainty is introduced in the mesoscale correction due to

the two dominant ways the precipitation pattern can contribute to the mesoscale domain. In any case, the linear fit represents a conservative mid-trend indicator which might not be representative of the precipitation behaviour during extreme events, as they are capture in the long-term climatic timeseries. A potential area of improvement would be the introduction of multi-variate or stateful interpolators, instead of the average trend line fit, in order to better capture the dynamics of this series.

Table 25: *Downscaled precipitation - related Indicators for the use case of Romania.*

Period	RX5day (mm)		R95pTOT (mm)		R99pTOT (mm)	
	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO	RCM	MEMO
Historical	9	22	383.48	965	207.46	522
2006–2040	12	30	332	835	147.32	370
2041–2070	7	17	350.15	881	137.79	346
2071–2100	13	32	350.33	881	274.34	690

6. Conclusions

This deliverable report presents the downscaling approaches and methods employed for large-scale climatological and meteorological data in the PLOTTO project and their applications to the use cases and the results. The large-scale data to be downscaled is on one hand RCM-predictions for the future climate scenarios and on the other hand NWP-model data for short term forecasts. The climatological data consists of several pairs of RCMs nested into GCMs and driven by three greenhouse-gas emission scenarios (representative concentration pathways, RCP): RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. This data is extracted from the EURO-CORDEX database (Kotlarski et al., 2014) for the PLOTTO use-case relevant areas, see Lehtonen et al (2023). Temporally the time series span from the beginning of the year 2006 up to the end of 2099 or 2100 depending on the model run. In addition, respective historical data spanning from the beginning of 1971 to the end of 2005 has been extracted from the EURO-CORDEX database by Lehtonen et al. (2023). The short-term NWP data used in this work is obtained from the ICON-EU NWP modelling system (Zängl et al., 2015).

As the resolution of the climatological and meteorological data is relatively low. The RCM and NWP models cannot capture any effects of local small-scale features of specific sites of interest like fine-grained terrain shape, buildings and trees. Therefore, the data is downscaled to local scale and high resolution such that the effects of the local features are properly captured.

We apply two downscaling approaches in this work. For wind data, we apply an approach based on precomputed very high resolution Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) data and data fusion. For other meteorological variables of interest: temperature, relative humidity, cloud cover and precipitation we apply high-resolution meso-scale modelling. These approaches and methods are described in the report.

The downscaled RCM data for future-climate scenarios will be used in WP4 for infrastructure resilience assessment. The short-term downscaled forecasting systems developed here will be used in WP6 to support IWAT, Decision support system and Enhanced Visualization Interface.

The report also describes the PLOTTO use cases and their relevant weather vulnerabilities and hazards. Finally, two preliminary application examples of downscaling are given.

Detailed conclusions from the downscaling studies and mesoscale results are presented in the end of each use-case sub chapter in Chapter **Error! Reference source not found..** The main messages can be crystallized as follows. When only wind is considered, the climate change has practically no impact on the wind conditions according to the climate modelling data in the studied use-case locations. There is no significant trend in the wind data and no significant differences between the RCP-scenarios and the historical data. The available wind data from the two RCMs RACMO22E and RCA4 differ remarkably from each other. Based on our validation in Use Case C, RACMO22E is in better agreement with the observations. Downscaling systematically makes the high wind-speed tail of the wind-speed probability density distribution somewhat stronger compared with the non-downscaled RCM results as seen especially from the 99th percentiles and the yearly exceedance counts. In Use Case C, it was found that the occurrence of heavy gust-episodes spatially varies surprisingly much over the river surface. It was found that in built environment, wind observations may underestimate the gust wind speeds in other nearby locations even at the elevation of the meteo station. The observation points cannot perfectly represent the wind conditions everywhere in a built area of interest such as the Budapest port. It became evident that wind shading and channelling by large buildings and structures

have significant effects on the local wind field and turbulence. In Use Case A two different target areas were studied: the open and flat sea-entrance area and the port area in built environment. Comparison of these two clearly showed the roughness effect on wind turbulence. The gusts are heavier and more frequent in the port area because of the town.

In the case of temperature, the main effect induced by climate change is a rapid decrease in the number of frost days and icing days by the end of the century. The mesoscale correction is causing an increase of this estimate for Use Cases C and A and a slight decrease for Use Case B, without affecting the overall climatic trend. Diurnal Temperature Range (DTR) uniformly shows a slight increase by the end of the century, however also looking at the monthly trends (Deliverable D3.4) reveals that the intra-annual variation tends to increase with time, indicating increasing month-to-month instability of the temperature extrema. The mesoscale correction is causing a linear increase of between 1 and 2 degrees Celsius in the predicted DTR compared to the RCM-provided index. The TN90p index (percentage of warm nights) shows a slight increase in the last quarter of the century, indicating that the bulk of any warming effect will shift the temperature distribution almost uniformly. On the other hand, the TN10p index (percentage of cold nights) shows very little variation across periods. The mesoscale corrections are not affecting these two percentile-based metrics, since they only induce a linear shift on the temperature distribution.

Regarding precipitation, different Regional Climate Models (RCMs) produce varying results for Romania, as detailed in PLOT0 Deliverables D3.1 and D3.4. While projections generally indicate a decrease in precipitation levels across Eastern Europe due to global warming, the impact in Romania is primarily observed at lower thresholds and shorter return periods. In terms of precipitation extremes, the representative CGM-RCM configuration presented in this report under the RCP4.5 scenario predicts an increase in the accumulated precipitation of very- and extremely wet days (R95pTOT and R99pTOT, respectively) for Wallonia and Romania, and to a smaller extent for Budapest. In terms of the wettest 5-day period (Rx5day) contribution, a consistent increasing trend of this extreme indicator is more evident for the Romanian/lower Danube area, less so for the other two cases. In all these cases, the mesoscale correction over the respective domains (roughly coinciding with the local catchment areas) is causing a significant but uniform increase in the assessment of total precipitation, which can be explained by the increased resolution of the assessment of precipitation height in the local domain. It can be deduced from these results that an overall increase in heavy precipitation events, which could elevate flood risks and challenge existing water management infrastructure in the region.

7. References

- Auvinen, M., Boi, S., Hellsten, A., Tanhuanpää, T. and Järvi, L.: Study of Realistic Urban Boundary Layer Turbulence with High-Resolution Large-Eddy Simulation. *Atmosphere* 2020, 11, 201. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos11020201>, 2020.
- Auvinen, M., Kuula, J. Grönholm, T., Sühling, M., Hellsten, A.; High-resolution large-eddy simulation of indoor turbulence and its effect on airborne transmission of respiratory pathogens—Model validation and infection probability analysis. *Physics of Fluids* 1 January 2022; 34 (1): 015124. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0076495>
- Deardorff, J.W.: Stratocumulus-capped mixed layers derived from a three-dimensional model, *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 18, 495-527, 1980.
- Favre, A., Philippon, N., Pohl, B., Kalognomou, E. A., & Lennard, C: DIAGNOSTIC DE LA VARIABILITÉ INTERANNUELLE DES SORTIES CORDEX-AFRICA SUR LE SECTEUR DE L'AFRIQUE DU SUD. In 27ème Colloque de l'Association Internationale de Climatologie (pp. 131-137). Association Internationale de Climatologie, 2014.
- Hellsten, A., Ketelsen, K., Sühling, M., Auvinen, M., Maronga, B., Knigge, C., Barmpas, F., Tsegas, G., Moussiopoulos, N., and Raasch, S.: A nested multi-scale system implemented in the large-eddy simulation model PALM model system 6.0, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 14, 3185–3214, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-14-3185-2021>, 2021.
- Kanda, M., Inagaki, A., Miyamoto, T., Gryschka, M., and Raasch, S.: A new aerodynamic parameterization for real urban surfaces, *Boundary-Layer Meteorology.*, 148, 357–377, 2013.
- Kotlarski, S., Keuler, K., Christensen, O. B., Colette, A., Déqué, M., Gobiet, A., Goergen, K., Jacob, D., Lüthi, D., van Meijgaard, E., Nikulin, G., Schär, C., Teichmann, C., Vautard, R., Warrach-Sagi, K., and Wulfmeyer, V.: Regional climate modeling on European scales: a joint standard evaluation of the EURO-CORDEX RCM ensemble. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 7: 1297–1333, doi:10.5194/gmd-7-1297-2014, 2014.
- Lehtonen, I., Hellsten, A., Auvinen, M., Barmpas, F. and Tsegas, G. High-resolution surface parameter maps, based on climate scenarios and available data. PLOT0 deliverable report D3.1, 2023.
- Maronga, B., Gryschka, M., Heinze, R., Hoffmann, F., Kanani-Sühling, F., Keck, M., Ketelsen, K., Letzel, M. O., Sühling, M., and Raasch, S.: The Parallelized Large-Eddy Simulation Model (PALM) version 4.0 for atmospheric and oceanic flows: model formulation, recent developments, and future perspectives, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 8, 2515–2551, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-2515-2015>, 2015.
- Maronga, B., Banzhaf, S., Burmeister, C., Esch, T., Forkel, R., Fröhlich, D., Fuka, V., Gehrke, K. F., Geletič, J., Giersch, S., Gronemeier, T., Groß, G., Heldens, W., Hellsten, A., Hoffmann, F., Inagaki, A., Kadasch, E., Kanani-Sühling, F., Ketelsen, K., Khan, B. A., Knigge, C., Knoop, H., Krč, P., Kurppa, M., Maamari, H., Matzarakis, A., Mauder, M., Pallasch, M., Pavlik, D., Pfafferoth, J., Resler, J., Rissmann, S., Russo, E., Salim, M., Schrempf, M., Schwenkel, J., Seckmeyer, G., Schubert, S., Sühling, M., von Tils, R., Vollmer, L., Ward, S., Witha, B., Wurps, H., Zeidler, J., and Raasch, S.: Overview of the PALM model system 6.0, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 13, 1335–1372, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-1335-2020>, 2020.
- Moussiopoulos, N. “The EUMAC Zooming Model, a tool for local-to-regional air quality studies,” *Meteorology and Atmospheric Physics*, vol. 57, no. 1–4, pp. 115–133, 1995.

Moussiopoulos N., Douros I., Tsegas G., Kleanthous S. and Chourdakis E.: An air quality management system for policy support in Cyprus, Hindawi Publishing Corporation, *Advances in Meteorology* 2012, doi:10.1155/2012/959280, 2012.

Saiki, E.M., Moeng, C.-H., and Sullivan, P.P.: Large-eddy simulation of the stably stratified planetary boundary layer, *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 95, 1-30, 2000.

Tank, Albert & Zwiers, Francis & Zhang, Xuebin.: *Guidelines on Analysis of Extremes in a Changing Climate in Support of Informed Decisions for Adaptation*. World Meteorological Organization, 2009.

Wallonair.be. Available from: <https://data.wallonair.be/>. Accessed 2024.

Wicker, L.J. and Skamarock, W.C.: Time-splitting methods for elastic models using forward time schemes, *Monthly Weather Reviews* 130, 2088-2097, 2002.

Williamson, J.H.: Low-storage Runge-Kutta schemes, *Journal of Computational Physics* 35, 48-56, 1980.

Zängl, G., D. Reinert, P. Ripodas, and M. Baldauf: The ICON (ICOsahedral Non-hydrostatic) modelling framework of DWD and MPI-M: Description of the non-hydrostatic dynamical core. *Q.J.R.Meteorol. Soc.*, 141, pp. 563–579, 2015.

URL1: <http://www2.jpl.nasa.gov/srtm/>

URL2: <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/corine-land-cover>